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Spectral continuity

THESIS

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Introduction

The idea of the spectrum of an operator in contemporary mathematics arises from various attempts to understand concrete problems of linear algebra that involve the solution of linear equations and their generalizations to infinite dimensions. However, this view is the result of the mathematical evolution of a series of ideas over three centuries. Spectral theory is a fundamental branch of mathematics that has had a strong impact on mathematical analysis and, in particular, on functional analysis, since it is related to results in different areas such as differential equations, integral equations, dynamical systems, quantum mechanics, among others.

Let X be a Banach space, the spectrum of a bounded operator $T : X \rightarrow X$, denoted by $\sigma(T)$, is the set of complex numbers λ , for which there does not exist a bounded operator $S : X \rightarrow X$ that satisfies $(\lambda - T)S = S(\lambda - T) = I$, that is,

$$\sigma(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda - T \text{ is not invertible in the space of bounded operators defined on } X\}.$$

The denomination of spectrum arises from the fact that the equation

$$(\lambda I - T)x = y, \quad \lambda \notin \sigma(T),$$

admits for each $y \in X$ one and only one solution $x \in X$. Many equations in mathematics are reduced in their abstract form to an equation of type above, for example, an integral equation

$$\lambda f(s) - \int_a^b k(t, s)f(t) dt = g(s),$$

where g is a function given in $C[a, b]$, f is the unknown, $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ and $k(s, t)$ is a continuous function in $[a, b] \times [a, b]$, can be thought of as an equation of the type

$$(\lambda I - T)f = g,$$

here T is the integral operator defined on the Banach space $C[a, b]$ as

$$(Tf)(s) := \int_a^b k(t, s)f(t) dt.$$

Thus, it is important to know in detail the properties of a spectrum, more precisely the properties of $\lambda I - T$ when λ belongs to the spectrum.

The present thesis is framed in the field of spectral theory of bounded operators and of

matrix operators defined on Banach spaces. In particular, in this project the continuity of the spectrum is investigated, viewed as a function of the space of bounded operators in the class of compact and nonempty subsets of the complex plane. We know that in practice it is often not possible to directly find eigenvalues, or any other spectral set, of a linear and bounded operator that interests us. In that case, one seeks a way to “approximate” in some sense the spectral value that we desire, and the study of the continuity of the spectrum using the Hausdorff metric takes an essential role.

The structure of this thesis is organized as follows. The first three chapters are devoted mainly to the presentation of known results.

In the first chapter, we introduce several classes of operators, including spectral projections, semi-Fredholm operators, operators with finite ascent and descent, and operators possessing the SVEP. We also discuss the relationships among these classes.

In the second chapter, we describe several important parts of the spectrum of an operator, namely the Fredholm spectrum, the Weyl spectrum, and the Browder spectrum. In addition, we study the classes of operators that satisfy Browder’s theorem and a-Browder’s theorem.

In the third chapter, we investigate the left-right essential spectrum following the ideas of Conway and Morrel in [13, Section 1], extending their approach to the class of operators defined on Banach spaces.

We dedicate the fourth chapter to the study of the continuity of the spectrum and its various parts. Newburgh (see [37]) was among the first to undertake a systematic investigation of spectral continuity. Since then, many authors have extensively studied this topic (see, for example, [13, 14, 15, 6, 11, 17, 18, 19, 20, 28]).

Conway and Morrel, in [14], characterized the continuity of the approximate point spectrum on the class of bounded operators defined on Hilbert spaces. Motivated by these results, in the third section of this chapter we establish new sufficient conditions, related to the concept of SVEP, for the continuity of the approximate point spectrum on the class of bounded operators defined on Banach spaces. In the fourth section, we prove that if T is a point of continuity of the spectrum, then T satisfies Browder’s theorem. An analogous result is obtained for the approximate point spectrum in connection with the a-Browder theorem. The first relation was also observed by S. V. Djordjević and Y. M. Han in [19], although in the context of the Browder spectrum. Finally, in the fifth section, we study the continuity of the spectrum under perturbations of the form $T + K$, where T is a bounded operator and K is a compact operator.

The spectral theory of matrix operators is a relatively recent and active area of research. One of the first important contributions in this direction was published in 1994 by Du and Pan (see [24]), and the subject was later developed in greater depth by W. Y. Lee, beginning with his article [32]. In recent years, several works concerning this topic have appeared in the literature (see [7, 8, 12, 23, 20, 22, 46]).

Following the line of research initiated in [20], in the fifth chapter of this thesis we study the continuity of the spectrum on the class of upper triangular matrix operators:

Let X and Y be Banach spaces, we denote by $B(X, Y)$ the space of linear and bounded

operators from X to Y , when $X = Y$ we only write $B(X)$. For $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$ let M_C be the operator defined over $X \oplus Y$ as

$$M_C = \begin{bmatrix} A & C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix}.$$

There are certain types of operators that can be decomposed as the previous matrix, for example, the operators T that are (p, k) -quasihyponormal are expressed as

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} T_1 & T_2 \\ 0 & T_3 \end{bmatrix},$$

where T_1 is a p -hyponormal operator and T_3 is k -nilpotent. Note that the operators in its diagonal are relatively simpler than the same operator T . As well as this example, there are many cases in which it is easier to study a spectral property of the operator M_C by examining the corresponding spectra property of operators A and B .

Then, a natural question concerning the continuity of the spectrum in M_C arises: assuming that the spectrum is continuous at A and B , what additional conditions must these operators satisfy in order to ensure that the spectrum function is continuous at M_C ? This question is addressed in Chapter 5.

All the results presented in Sections 3–5 of Chapter 4 are original. In Chapter 5, Theorem 5.15 in Section 1 is original, and all the results established in Section 2 are original as well. These contributions are contained in the following articles:

- INTERNATIONAL REFEREED JOURNALS:

1. S. Sánchez-Perales, S. V. Djordjević, Continuity of spectrum and approximate point spectrum on operator matrices, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 378 (2011) 289–294.
2. S. Sánchez-Perales, S. V. Djordjević, Continuity of spectra and compact perturbations, *Bulletin of the Korean Mathematical Society*, 48 (2011), 1261–1270 .

- OTHER REFEREED PUBLICATIONS:

1. S. Sánchez Perales, Continuity of the spectrum in unilateral shifts of finite multiplicity, included in the proceedings of the Fifth National Week of Mathematics, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla, México, 2010.

Chapter 1

An Introduction to Bounded Operators

In this first chapter, we present, in a general manner, the fundamental elements and basic concepts necessary for the development of this work. We also include several important results concerning the relationships among the concepts introduced here and those that will be used throughout the subsequent chapters. Furthermore, appropriate references to the original bibliographic sources are provided, where the details of the notions and results discussed in this chapter can be found.

1.1 Preliminaries

Let X and Y be Banach spaces over the complex plane \mathbb{C} . Let us denote by $B(X, Y)$ the set of bounded linear operators defined from X into Y , when $X = Y$ we will only denote it by $B(X)$. This set, with the usual operations of addition and multiplication by a scalar, is a vector space; moreover, $B(X)$ is an algebra with the multiplication given by $(T, S) \mapsto T \circ S$.

Now, if we endow $B(X)$ with the norm $\|T\| = \inf\{\beta \geq 0 : \|Tx\| \leq \beta\|x\| \text{ for all } x \in X\}$, then $B(X)$ is a Banach algebra with identity.

Consider X^* and Y^* the duals of X and Y , that is, $X^* = B(X, \mathbb{C})$ and $Y^* = B(Y, \mathbb{C})$. For $T \in B(X, Y)$ the adjoint operator $T^* : Y^* \rightarrow X^*$ of T is defined as:

$$(T^* f^*)(x) = f^*(Tx)$$

for any $f^* \in Y^*$ and $x \in X$. It is evident that this operator is linear; moreover, it is a bounded operator since $\|T^*\| = \|T\|$. Some relations between T and T^* are stated below.

For $T, S \in B(X, Y)$ and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2 \in \mathbb{C}$ it holds that

$$(\lambda_1 T + \lambda_2 S)^* = \lambda_1 T^* + \lambda_2 S^*.$$

Clearly, the adjoint of the identity operator in $B(X)$ is the identity operator in $B(X^*)$. Now, suppose that $A : Y \rightarrow Z$ and $T : X \rightarrow Y$ are bounded operators; then we can take their composition $AT : X \rightarrow Z$ and also its adjoint $(AT)^* : Z^* \rightarrow X^*$. In this case it is verified that

$$(AT)^* = T^* A^*.$$

From this, it follows that, if T is invertible, then

$$(T^*)^{-1} = (T^{-1})^*.$$

Let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a bounded linear operator, the kernel of T , denoted by $N(T)$, is defined as

$$N(T) = \{x \in X \mid Tx = 0\},$$

and the range of T , denoted by $R(T)$, as

$$R(T) = \{Tx \mid x \in X\}.$$

Theorem 1.1. *For any $T \in B(X)$, it holds that $R(T)$ is closed if and only if $R(T^*)$ is closed.*

Let S and W be, respectively, linear subspaces of X and X^* . Define

$$S^\perp = \{x^* \in X^* \mid x^*(x) = 0 \text{ for all } x \in S\}$$

and

$${}^\perp W = \{x \in X \mid x^*(x) = 0 \text{ for all } x^* \in W\}.$$

It can be proved, using for example [35, Corollary 4.63], that if S is closed, then ${}^\perp(S^\perp) = S$.

Lemma 1.2. *For every closed linear subspace E of X , E^* is isometrically isomorphic to X^*/E^\perp .*

The following duality relations between the kernel and the range of an operator T and its adjoint T^* are given, see for example, [33, p. 159]:

$$N(T) = {}^\perp \overline{R(T^*)} \quad \text{and} \quad {}^\perp N(T^*) = \overline{R(T)} \tag{1.1}$$

$$\overline{R(T)}^\perp = N(T^*) \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{R(T^*)} \subseteq N(T)^\perp. \tag{1.2}$$

The last inclusion is, in general, strict. However, a classical result establishes that equality holds when $R(T)$ is closed. Indeed:

Theorem 1.3. *If $R(T)$ is closed, then $R(T^*) = N(T)^\perp$.*

An operator $T \in B(X)$ is said to be bounded below if T is injective and has closed range. As an immediate consequence of the equalities shown in (1.1) and (1.2) and of the previous theorem, we obtain the following result.

Proposition 1.4. *Let $T \in B(X)$. Then T is surjective (resp. bounded below) if and only if T^* is bounded below (resp. surjective).*

We now turn to spectral theory, a fundamental area in operator theory and a central topic of this thesis. As noted above, $B(X)$ is an algebra; therefore, it is natural to consider which

of its elements are invertible. In this way, for an operator $T \in B(X)$, we can define the set

$$\rho(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda - T \text{ is invertible in } B(X)\}.$$

This set is called the resolvent of T . Its complement, an even more interesting set, is denoted by $\sigma(T)$ and is known as the spectrum of T . That is,

$$\sigma(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda - T \text{ is not invertible in } B(X)\}.$$

It is known that this is a compact and nonempty subset of \mathbb{C} . In fact, it is bounded by $\|T\|$, that is, $\sigma(T) \subseteq B(0, \|T\|)$.

The spectral radius $r(T)$ of an operator $T \in B(X)$ is defined as

$$r(T) = \sup\{|\lambda| \mid \lambda \in \sigma(T)\}.$$

Clearly $r(T) \leq \|T\|$, moreover, it can be proved, see for example [16, p. 25], that if $T \in B(X)$, then the limit $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|T^n\|^{1/n}$ exists and is equal to $r(T)$.

Example 1.5. We present below the spectra of certain operators:

- (a) When X is a Banach space of finite dimension and $T \in B(X)$, the spectrum of T consists of the eigenvalues of T .
- (b) Let the multiplication operator $T : L^2[0, 1] \rightarrow L^2[0, 1]$ be defined as $(Tf)(t) = tf(t)$. Then $\sigma(T) = [0, 1]$.
- (c) See [42]. Let $\ell^2(\mathbb{N}) = \{\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset \mathbb{C} \mid \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |x_n|^2 < \infty\}$. This is a Hilbert space with inner product

$$\langle \{x_n\}, \{y_n\} \rangle = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} x_n \overline{y_n}.$$

Consider $U : \ell^2(\mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \ell^2(\mathbb{N})$ defined by

$$U(x) = (0, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots), \quad x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots).$$

This operator, usually known as unilateral shift, has spectrum

$$\sigma(U) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}.$$

- (d) Let H be a Hilbert space. The spectrum of each unitary operator $T \in B(H)$ is contained in $\{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}$. In particular, let $L^2(\mathbb{T})$ be the space of square integrable functions on the circle \mathbb{T} and let $a \in \mathbb{T}$. The translation operator $T_a : L^2(\mathbb{T}) \rightarrow L^2(\mathbb{T})$ defined by $(T_a f)(x) = f(x - a)$ is a unitary operator and, therefore, $\sigma(T_a) \subseteq \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}$.

The spectrum of a bounded operator can be divided into subsets of \mathbb{C} in different ways, and each one of these subsets is known as parts of the spectrum. For $T \in B(X)$, the surjective

spectrum and the approximate point spectrum of T are defined, respectively, as

$$\sigma_{su}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda - T \text{ is not surjective}\}$$

and

$$\sigma_{ap}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda - T \text{ is not bounded below}\}.$$

It is known that T is bounded below if and only if there exists $K > 0$ such that

$$K\|x\| \leq \|Tx\|,$$

for all $x \in X$. From this it follows easily that $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(T)$ if and only if there exists a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X such that $\|x_n\| = 1$ and $(\lambda - T)x_n \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. From this it can be proved that $\sigma_{ap}(T)$ is a closed and nonempty subset of \mathbb{C} , moreover,

$$\partial\sigma(T) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(T).$$

Observe, from the definitions of the surjective spectrum and the approximate point spectrum, that

$$\sigma(T) = \sigma_{su}(T) \cup \sigma_{ap}(T).$$

There also exist duality relations between the surjective spectrum and the approximate point spectrum and vice versa. Indeed, by Proposition 1.4, the following equalities hold:

$$\sigma(T) = \sigma(T^*), \quad \sigma_{ap}(T) = \sigma_{su}(T^*), \quad \sigma_{ap}(T^*) = \sigma_{su}(T).$$

To conclude this section, we present the definition of the point spectrum of an operator $T \in B(X)$. This is the set, denoted by $\sigma_p(T)$, that consists of all eigenvalues of T , where recall that a number $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ is an eigenvalue of T if there exists a nonzero element $x \in X$ such that $(\lambda - T)x = 0$. For each $\lambda \in \sigma_p(T)$, clearly $\lambda - T$ is not injective. Thus,

$$\sigma_p(T) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(T).$$

1.2 Spectral Projections

Functions of a complex variable with values in the Banach algebra $B(X)$, where X is a Banach space, play an important role in spectral theory, as well as in what follows in this thesis. Let Ω be a nonempty open subset of \mathbb{C} , we say that $F : \Omega \rightarrow B(X)$ is analytic in Ω if for every $z_0 \in \Omega$, the limit

$$F'(z_0) := \lim_{z \rightarrow z_0} \frac{F(z) - F(z_0)}{z - z_0}$$

exists. As an example, for each $T \in B(X)$, the function $(z - T)^{-1}$ is analytic in the set $\rho(T)$.

A curve γ in \mathbb{C} is a continuous function $\gamma : [a, b] \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$. It is said to be closed

if $\gamma(a) = \gamma(b)$. A closed curve is called simple if for each $t_1, t_2 \in [a, b]$ with $t_1 < t_2$ and $\gamma(t_1) = \gamma(t_2)$ implies that $t_1 = a$ and $t_2 = b$. In this case we identify γ with its image $\gamma([a, b])$. A Jordan curve γ in \mathbb{C} is a simple closed curve that is rectifiable.

An elementary Cauchy domain is a subset of \mathbb{C} that is open, connected and bounded whose boundary is the union of a finite number of Jordan curves that do not intersect each other. A finite union of elementary Cauchy domains whose closures do not intersect each other is called a Cauchy domain.

Theorem 1.6. *Let Ω be an open subset of \mathbb{C} . If E is a compact subset of \mathbb{C} such that $E \subseteq \Omega$, then there exists a Cauchy domain D such that*

$$E \subseteq D \subseteq \overline{D} \subseteq \Omega.$$

Let D be a Cauchy domain. If each Jordan curve involved in the boundary of D is oriented in the positive sense, then the oriented boundary C of D is called a Cauchy contour.

Let E_1, E_2 be subsets of \mathbb{C} . If C is a Cauchy contour determined by a Cauchy domain D such that $E_1 \subseteq D$ and $E_2 \subseteq \mathbb{C} \setminus (D \cup C)$, then we say that C separates E_1 from E_2 .

Let $T \in B(X)$. A subset Λ of $\sigma(T)$ that is open and closed in $\sigma(T)$ is called a spectral set of T . The set $\{\lambda\}$ formed by an isolated point λ of $\sigma(T)$ is a spectral set of T .

Corollary 1.7. *For each spectral set Λ of T , there exists a Cauchy contour C that separates Λ from $\sigma(T) \setminus \Lambda$.*

Let $\gamma : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a curve in \mathbb{C} of bounded variation. For $F : \gamma([a, b]) \rightarrow B(X)$ continuous, we define the contour integral of F along γ as

$$\int_{\gamma} F(z) dz := \int_a^b F(\gamma(t)) d\gamma(t), \quad (1.3)$$

where the integral on the right is an element of $B(X)$ that satisfies that, for each $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that if $P = \{t_0 < t_1 < \dots < t_n\}$ is a partition of $[a, b]$ with $\|P\| < \delta$, then

$$\left\| \int_a^b F(\gamma(t)) d\gamma(t) - \sum_{i=1}^n F(s_i) (\gamma(t_i) - \gamma(t_{i-1})) \right\| < \varepsilon,$$

for any choice of the points $s_i \in [t_{i-1}, t_i]$. The contour integral in (1.3) exists and is unique; moreover, the theory of contour integration of complex-valued functions can be extended with minimal changes to this general context.

Let $T \in B(X)$ and Λ a spectral set of T . We define the spectral projection corresponding to T and Λ as follows:

$$P(T, \Lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C (z - T)^{-1} dz$$

where C is a Cauchy contour that separates Λ from $\sigma(T) \setminus \Lambda$. Observe that the definition of P is well-defined since the integral does not depend on the choice of the contour C , because

any other Cauchy contour \tilde{C} that separates Λ from $\sigma(T) \setminus \Lambda$ can be continuously deformed in the resolvent of T into C .

Remark 1.8. Let $T \in B(X)$ and Λ a spectral set of T . Some main properties of $P := P(T, \Lambda)$ are the following:

(a) $P \in B(X)$ and $P^2 = P$, that is, P is a bounded projection. Therefore,

$$N(P) = R(I - P) \quad \text{and} \quad R(P) = N(I - P)$$

are closed subspaces of X such that

$$X = R(P) \oplus N(P).$$

(b) P commutes with T , thus $N(P)$ and $R(P)$ are invariant subspaces under T .

(c) If $L_1 : N(P) \rightarrow N(P)$ and $L_2 : R(P) \rightarrow R(P)$ are operators defined as $L_1 = T|_{N(P)}$ and $L_2 = T|_{R(P)}$, then

$$\sigma(L_1) = \sigma(T) \setminus \Lambda \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma(L_2) = \Lambda.$$

(d) $P = 0$ if and only if $\Lambda = \emptyset$, and $P = I$ if and only if $\Lambda = \sigma(T)$.

Let $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$, that is, λ is an isolated point of $\sigma(T)$. Denote by $P(T, \lambda)$ the spectral projection corresponding to T and $\{\lambda\}$. With this notation, we are now in a position to state the following theorem.

Theorem 1.9. *Let $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$ and $P := P(T, \lambda)$. Then*

(a)

$$\bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} N(\lambda - T)^j \subseteq R(P) \quad \text{and} \quad N(P) \subseteq \bigcap_{j=1}^{\infty} R(\lambda - T)^j.$$

(b) *If $\dim R(P) = m < \infty$, then $R(P) = N(\lambda - T)^m$ and $N(P) = R(\lambda - T)^m$. Moreover, λ is an eigenvalue of T .*

Proof. See [1, Proposition 1.31]. □

Theorem 1.10. *Let Λ be a nonempty spectral set of $T \in B(X)$ and let $P := P(T, \Lambda)$. Then $\dim R(P) < \infty$ if and only if $\Lambda = \{\lambda_1, \dots, \lambda_r\}$, where for each $j = 1, \dots, r$, $\lambda_j \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$ and the range of $P_j := P(T, \lambda_j)$ is finite dimensional.*

Proof. See [1, Theorem 1.32]. □

Let $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in $B(X)$. We say that T_n converges to a bounded operator T , and write $T_n \rightarrow T$, if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|T_n - T\| = 0$.

In what follows, we study the relationship between the spectral projections of T_n and that of T under the assumption that $T_n \rightarrow T$.

Lemma 1.11. [1, Theorem 2.6] Let $T \in B(X)$ and E a closed and nonempty subset of $\rho(T) = \mathbb{C} \setminus \sigma(T)$. Then

$$(a) \alpha_1(E) := \sup\{\|(z - T)^{-1}\| \mid z \in E\} < \infty,$$

(b) if $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence in $B(X)$ that converges to T , then there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $n \geq n_0$, $E \subseteq \rho(T_n)$, and

$$\alpha_2(E) := \sup\{\|(z - T_n)^{-1}\| \mid z \in E, n \geq n_0\} < \infty.$$

Theorem 1.12. Let Λ be a spectral set of $T \in B(X)$ and C a Cauchy contour that separates Λ from $\sigma(T) \setminus \Lambda$. If $\{T_n\}$ is a sequence in $B(X)$ such that $T_n \rightarrow T$, then:

(a) There exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $n \geq n_0$, C is contained in $\rho(T_n)$. Moreover, if D is the Cauchy domain determined by C , then for $n \geq n_0$, $\Lambda_n = \sigma(T_n) \cap D$ is a spectral set for T_n , and C separates Λ_n from $\sigma(T_n) \setminus \Lambda_n$.

$$(b) \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} P(T_n, \Lambda_n) = P(T, \Lambda),$$

(c) there exists $n_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ with $n_1 \geq n_0$, such that for each $n \geq n_1$,

$$\dim R(P_n) = \dim R(P),$$

where $P_n := P(T_n, \Lambda_n)$ and $P := P(T, \Lambda)$.

Proof. (a) By Lemma 1.11, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $n \geq n_0$, $C \subseteq \rho(T_n)$. Let $n \geq n_0$. Observe that $\Lambda_n \subseteq D$ and $\sigma(T_n) \setminus \Lambda_n \subseteq \mathbb{C} \setminus (D \cup C)$, that is, C separates Λ_n from $\sigma(T_n) \setminus \Lambda_n$. Clearly, Λ_n is open in $\sigma(T_n)$, since D is open in \mathbb{C} . On the other hand, since

$$\sigma(T_n) \setminus \Lambda_n = \sigma(T_n) \cap (\mathbb{C} \setminus (D \cup C))$$

and $\mathbb{C} \setminus (D \cup C)$ is open in \mathbb{C} , it follows that Λ_n is also closed in $\sigma(T_n)$.

(b) Let $n \geq n_0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \|P(T_n, \Lambda_n) - P(T, \Lambda)\| &= \left\| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C [(z - T_n)^{-1} - (z - T)^{-1}] dz \right\| \\ &= \left\| \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C (z - T_n)^{-1} (T_n - T) (z - T)^{-1} dz \right\|. \end{aligned}$$

Now, by Lemma 1.11,

$$\|(z - T_n)^{-1} (T_n - T) (z - T)^{-1}\| \leq \alpha_1(C) \alpha_2(C) \|T_n - T\|$$

for all $z \in C$. Hence,

$$\left\| \int_C (z - T_n)^{-1} (T_n - T) (z - T)^{-1} dz \right\| \leq \alpha_1(C) \alpha_2(C) \|T_n - T\| V_C,$$

where V_C is the finite sum of the variations of all the Jordan curves that make up C . Thus,

$$\|P(T_n, \Lambda_n) - P(T, \Lambda)\| \leq \frac{V_C}{2\pi} \alpha_1(C) \alpha_2(C) \|T_n - T\|.$$

(c) From part (b), we have that $P_n \rightarrow P$, thus

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} r(P_n - P) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|P_n - P\| = 0.$$

That is, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} r(P_n - P) = 0$. With this, we can take $n_1 \geq n_0$ such that, for each $n \geq n_1$, $I - (P_n - P)$ and $I - (P - P_n)$ are invertible in $B(X)$.

Let $n \geq n_1$. We verify that $P|_{R(P_n)} : R(P_n) \rightarrow R(P)$ is bijective. If $x \in N(P|_{R(P_n)})$, then $x \in R(P_n)$ and $Px = 0$, hence $[I - (P_n - P)]x = 0$, so $x \in N(I - (P_n - P))$, and since $N(I - (P_n - P)) = \{0\}$, it follows that $P|_{R(P_n)}$ is injective. Now, let $y \in R(P)$, then $P_y = y$. There exists $w \in X$ such that $[I - (P - P_n)]w = y$, hence $Pw - PPw + PP_nw = y$, and therefore $PP_nw = y$. Thus $P|_{R(P_n)}$ is surjective. \square

1.3 Semi-Fredholm Operators

We now introduce some important classes in Fredholm theory. Let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a bounded operator. We define the number $\alpha(T)$ as the dimension of $N(T)$ if $\dim N(T)$ is finite; otherwise, we set $\alpha(T) = \infty$. If $R(T)$ is closed, we also define $\beta(T)$ as the dimension of $X/R(T)$ if $\dim X/R(T)$ is finite; otherwise, we set $\beta(T) = \infty$. A result of Kato asserts that if $X/R(T)$ is finite dimensional, then $R(T)$ is a closed subspace of X .

We say that T is a semi-Fredholm operator if $R(T)$ is closed and $\alpha(T) < \infty$ or $\beta(T) < \infty$. The set of semi-Fredholm operators is denoted by $\Phi_{\pm}(X)$. Semi-Fredholm operators T for which $\alpha(T) < \infty$ are called upper semi-Fredholm operators, and the set of these operators is denoted by $\Phi_+(X)$. Similarly, semi-Fredholm operators T with $\beta(T) < \infty$ are called lower semi-Fredholm operators, and the set of these is denoted by $\Phi_-(X)$. Given a semi-Fredholm operator T , the index of T , denoted by $i(T)$, is defined as

$$i(T) = \alpha(T) - \beta(T).$$

A particular subclass of semi-Fredholm operators are Fredholm operators. An operator $T \in B(X)$ is Fredholm if $R(T)$ is closed, $\alpha(T) < \infty$ and $\beta(T) < \infty$. The set of such operators is denoted by $\Phi(X)$. Clearly, every invertible operator in $B(X)$ is a Fredholm operator. Also, any operator defined on a finite-dimensional Banach space into itself is a Fredholm operator. The unilateral shift $U(x) = (0, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots)$, $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots)$, presented in Example 1.5 (c), is also a Fredholm operator and $i(U) = -1$.

Remark 1.13. We now highlight some classical properties concerning the algebraic and topological nature of the class of semi-Fredholm operators.

(a) If $T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $S \in \Phi_+(X)$, then $TS \in \Phi_+(X)$. In fact, one also has that if T and

S are such that $\alpha(T) < \infty$ and $\alpha(S) < \infty$, then $\alpha(TS) < \infty$. Similarly, if $U \in \Phi_-(X)$ and $V \in \Phi_-(X)$, then $UV \in \Phi_-(X)$. In this way, $\Phi_+(X)$ and $\Phi_-(X)$ are multiplicative semigroups of $B(X)$ (see [16, Corollary 1.3.3]). Moreover, when $T \in \Phi(X)$ and $S \in \Phi(X)$, then $TS \in \Phi(X)$ and

$$i(TS) = i(T) + i(S),$$

see [33, Theorem 23.1].

(b) Let $T, S \in B(X)$. If $TS \in \Phi_+(X)$, then $S \in \Phi_+(X)$. Similarly, if $TS \in \Phi_-(X)$, then $T \in \Phi_-(X)$.

(c) The classes $\Phi_+(X)$ and $\Phi_-(X)$ are mutually dual, in the following sense:

$$T \in \Phi_+(X) \iff T^* \in \Phi_-(X^*)$$

and

$$T \in \Phi_-(X) \iff T^* \in \Phi_+(X^*).$$

Moreover,

$$\alpha(T^*) = \beta(T), \quad \alpha(T) = \beta(T^*), \quad \alpha(T) = \alpha(T^{**}),$$

see [16, pp. 7–8].

(d) For each $T \in \Phi_+(X)$, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that if an operator $S \in B(X)$ satisfies $\|S\| < \varepsilon$, then $T + S \in \Phi_+(X)$. Moreover,

$$\alpha(T + S) \leq \alpha(T) \quad \text{and} \quad i(T + S) = i(T).$$

Similarly, given $T \in \Phi_-(X)$, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that if $S \in B(X)$ satisfies $\|S\| < \varepsilon$, then $T + S \in \Phi_-(X)$, and

$$\beta(T + S) \leq \beta(T) \quad \text{and} \quad i(T + S) = i(T).$$

From this, it follows immediately that the semigroups $\Phi_+(X)$ and $\Phi_-(X)$ are open in $B(X)$, and the index function $i : \Phi_{\pm}(X) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \cup \{\pm\infty\}$ is continuous. The proof of this important result can be found in Caradus, Pfaffenberger, and Yood [16, pp. 61–64].

A class of particular importance in $B(X)$ is that of compact operators, denoted by $K(X)$. Recall that an operator $T \in B(X)$ is compact if, for every bounded sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X , the sequence $\{Tx_n\}$ has a convergent subsequence in X . It is well known that $K(X)$ forms a two-sided ideal of $B(X)$. Consequently, one can define the Calkin algebra on X as the quotient

$$C(X) = B(X)/K(X).$$

Moreover, $K(X)$ is a closed subspace of $B(X)$; thus $C(X)$, with the norm

$$\|T + K(X)\| = \inf_{U \in K(X)} \|T + U\|,$$

is a Banach algebra. We will use π to denote the canonical homomorphism from $B(X)$ into $C(X)$:

$$\pi(T) = T + K(X).$$

Remark 1.14. Semi-Fredholm operators, compact operators, and some of their relationships are summarized as follows:

(a) Let $T \in B(X)$. Then there exist operators $V \in B(X)$ and $K \in K(X)$ such that

$$VT = I + K,$$

if and only if $T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and there exists a bounded projection from X onto $R(T)$.

Similarly, there exist operators $U \in B(X)$ and $K \in K(X)$ such that

$$TU = I + K,$$

if and only if $T \in \Phi_-(X)$ and there exists a bounded projection from X onto $N(T)$.

A proof of this result can be found in [16, pp. 63–65].

(b) If $T \in \Phi_+(X)$ (respectively, $T \in \Phi_-(X)$) and K is a compact operator, then $T + K \in \Phi_+(X)$ (respectively, $T + K \in \Phi_-(X)$). Moreover,

$$i(T + K) = i(T).$$

We say that a closed linear subspace E of a Banach space X is complemented in X if there exists a closed linear subspace F of X such that $X = E \oplus F$. This property can also be characterized as follows: E is complemented in X if and only if there exists a bounded projection P from X onto E .

Let Z be a Banach algebra with identity. Denote by $G_l(Z)$ and $G_r(Z)$ the sets of elements that are left invertible and right invertible in Z , respectively. The sets $G_l(Z)$ and $G_r(Z)$ are open subsets of Z , see for example [16, Theorem 2.1.3]. For the Banach algebra $B(X)$ it is known that $T \in G_l(B(X))$ if and only if $N(T) = \{0\}$ and $R(T)$ is closed and complemented in X . Also, $T \in G_r(B(X))$ if and only if $R(T) = X$ and $N(T)$ is complemented in X .

Using the properties stated in Remark 1.14 (a), we obtain the following theorem, which shows a relation between the elements that are left or right invertible in the Calkin algebra $C(X)$ and the semi-Fredholm operators.

Theorem 1.15. *Let $\pi : B(X) \rightarrow C(X)$ be the canonical homomorphism. For $T \in B(X)$, the following equivalences hold:*

(a) $\lambda - \pi(T) \in G_l(C(X))$ if and only if $\lambda - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $R(\lambda - T)$ is complemented in X ;

(b) $\lambda - \pi(T) \in G_r(C(X))$ if and only if $\lambda - T \in \Phi_-(X)$ and $N(\lambda - T)$ is complemented in X .

Proof. (a) Suppose that $\lambda - \pi(T) \in G_l(C(X))$, that is, there exists $S \in B(X)$ such that

$$(S + K(X))(\lambda + K(X) - (T + K(X))) = I + K(X).$$

Simplifying this expression, we see that $\lambda S - ST + K(X) = I + K(X)$, which implies that $\lambda S - ST - I \in K(X)$. Thus, since

$$S(\lambda - T) = I + [\lambda S - ST - I],$$

we obtain, by Remark 1.14 (a), that $\lambda - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and that there exists a bounded projection of X onto $R(\lambda - T)$, equivalently $\lambda - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $R(\lambda - T)$ is complemented in X . The converse implication follows by reversing this argument. \square

Corollary 1.16. *Let $\pi : B(X) \rightarrow C(X)$ be the canonical homomorphism. Then $T \in B(X)$ is a Fredholm operator if and only if $\pi(T)$ is invertible in the Calkin algebra $C(X)$.*

1.4 The Ascent and Descent of an Operator

For $T, S \in B(X)$, it holds that $R(TS) \subseteq R(T)$ and $N(S) \subseteq N(TS)$. Define $T^0 = I$. Then

$$X = R(T^0) \supseteq R(T) \supseteq R(T^2) \supseteq \cdots \supseteq R(T^n) \supseteq R(T^{n+1}) \supseteq \cdots,$$

and also

$$\{0\} = N(T^0) \subseteq N(T) \subseteq N(T^2) \subseteq \cdots \subseteq N(T^n) \subseteq N(T^{n+1}) \subseteq \cdots.$$

The hyperkernel of T , denoted by $N^\infty(T)$, is defined as

$$N^\infty(T) = \bigcup_{n=0}^{\infty} N(T^n),$$

and the hyperrange of T , denoted by $R^\infty(T)$, by

$$R^\infty(T) = \bigcap_{n=0}^{\infty} R(T^n).$$

From their definitions, it follows immediately that these are T -invariant subspaces of X .

Proposition 1.17. *For $T \in B(X)$, the following inclusions are equivalent:*

- (a) $N(T) \subseteq R^\infty(T)$;
- (b) $N^\infty(T) \subseteq R(T)$;
- (c) $N^\infty(T) \subseteq R^\infty(T)$.

From the sequences of subspaces formed respectively by the kernels and ranges of the powers of a bounded operator, two important parameters associated with the operator are also derived:

The ascent of T , denoted by $p(T)$, and the descent of T , denoted by $q(T)$, are respectively the smallest nonnegative integer n such that $N(T^n) = N(T^{n+1})$, and $R(T^n) = R(T^{n+1})$. If such an n does not exist, we set $p(T) = \infty$ and $q(T) = \infty$.

Clearly, $p(T) = 0$ if and only if T is injective, and $q(T) = 0$ if and only if T is surjective. Now, if $R(T)$ is closed or $R(T^*)$ is closed, then by Theorem 1.3 and one of the equalities in (1.1), we have

$$p(T) = q(T^*) \quad \text{and} \quad q(T) = p(T^*). \quad (1.4)$$

Lemma 1.18. *Let $T \in B(X)$ and $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Then the following statements hold:*

(a) $p(T) \leq m < \infty$ if and only if, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$R(T^m) \cap N(T^n) = \{0\};$$

(b) $q(T) \leq m < \infty$ if and only if, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists a subspace $Y_n \subseteq N(T^m)$ such that

$$X = Y_n \oplus R(T^n).$$

Proof. See [2, Lemma 3.2]. □

Theorem 1.19. *If both $p(T)$ and $q(T)$ are finite, then $p(T) = q(T)$.*

The following proposition provides some fundamental relationships among the quantities $p(T)$, $q(T)$, $\alpha(T)$, and $\beta(T)$.

Theorem 1.20. *For $T \in B(X)$, the following statements hold:*

(a) *If $p(T) < \infty$, then $\alpha(T) \leq \beta(T)$;*

(b) *If $q(T) < \infty$, then $\beta(T) \leq \alpha(T)$;*

(c) *If $p(T) = q(T) < \infty$, then $\alpha(T) = \beta(T)$ (with the possibility that $\alpha(T) = \beta(T) = \infty$);*

(d) *If $\alpha(T) = \beta(T) < \infty$ and if $p(T)$ or $q(T)$ is finite, then $p(T) = q(T)$.*

Proof. (a) Let $p = p(T) < \infty$. If $\beta(T) = \infty$ there is nothing to prove. Suppose $\beta(T) < \infty$. By Remark 1.13 (a), $\beta(T^p) < \infty$. Now, by Lemma 1.18 (a), $N(T^p) \cap R(T^p) = \{0\}$, which implies that

$$\dim N(T^p) = \dim \frac{N(T^p) \oplus R(T^p)}{R(T^p)} \leq \dim \frac{X}{R(T^p)}.$$

Thus $\alpha(T^p) < \infty$. Using Remark 1.13 (a) and the fact that $N(T^n) = N(T^p)$ for any $n \geq p$, we obtain that

$$n \cdot i(T) = i(T^n) = \alpha(T^p) - \beta(T^n)$$

for any $n \geq p$. Observe that if $q(T) < \infty$ (which implies that $p = q(T)$), then $R(T^n) = R(T^p)$ for all $n \geq p$. Thus,

$$n \cdot i(T) = \alpha(T^p) - \beta(T^p).$$

for each natural number $n \geq p$. Consequently, $i(T) = 0$, that is, $\alpha(T) = \beta(T)$.

Now, if $q(T) = \infty$, then $\beta(T^n) \rightarrow \infty$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. In this way, $n \cdot i(T)$ will eventually become negative, hence $i(T) < 0$. Thus, in this case we have $\alpha(T) < \beta(T)$.

(b) Let $q = q(T) < \infty$. Suppose that $\alpha(T) < \infty$. By Remark 1.13 (a), $\alpha(T^q) < \infty$, and by Lemma 1.18 (b), for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $X = Y_n \oplus R(T^n)$ with $Y_n \subseteq N(T^q)$. From this it follows that

$$\beta(T^n) = \dim Y_n \leq \alpha(T^q) < \infty$$

for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Thus, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\beta(T^n) = \beta(T^{n_0})$ for all $n \geq n_0$. Therefore,

$$n \cdot i(T) = \alpha(T^n) - \beta(T^{n_0})$$

for each $n \geq n_0$. This implies that $\beta(T) = \alpha(T)$ when $p(T) < \infty$, and $\beta(T) < \alpha(T)$ when $p(T) = \infty$.

(c) If $p(T) = q(T) = d < \infty$, then $X = N(T^d) \oplus R(T^d)$, and this implies that $\alpha(T^d) = \beta(T^d)$. Therefore, $\alpha(T) = \beta(T)$.

(d) This part follows from the fact that

$$\forall n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad \alpha(T^n) - \beta(T^n) = n \cdot i(T) = 0.$$

□

Recall that an operator $T \in B(X)$ is said to be nilpotent if there exists $d \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $T^d = 0$, and T is quasinilpotent if $\sigma(T) = \{0\}$. By the spectral mapping theorem, it follows that if T is nilpotent, then T is quasinilpotent.

Lemma 1.21. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be non-invertible. If $p(T)$ and $q(T)$ are finite with common value $p \neq 0$, then*

(a) $X = R(T^p) \oplus N(T^p)$;

(b) the subspaces $R(T^p)$ and $N(T^p)$ are closed in X and invariant under T ;

(c) if $T_1 : R(T^p) \rightarrow R(T^p)$ and $T_2 : N(T^p) \rightarrow N(T^p)$ are defined by $T_1 = T|_{R(T^p)}$ and $T_2 = T|_{N(T^p)}$, then T_1 is injective and surjective, and T_2 is nilpotent;

(d) if $R(T^p)$ is closed, then there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $p(\lambda I - T) = 0$ for all $0 < |\lambda| < \varepsilon$;

(e) if $\alpha(T) < \infty$, then $0 \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$ and the spectral projection $P := P(T, 0)$ satisfies $R(P) = N(T^p)$ and $N(P) = R(T^p)$.

Proof. We prove only (d) and (e).

(d) By contradiction. Let $\{\lambda_n\} \subset \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ be such that $\lambda_n \rightarrow 0$ and for each n , $p(\lambda_n I - T) > 0$. Then there exists $\{x_n\} \subset X$ such that $\|x_n\| = 1$ and $Tx_n = \lambda_n x_n$. Observe that $N(\lambda_n I - T) \subseteq R(T^p)$, since if $s \in N(\lambda_n I - T)$, then $s = \frac{1}{\lambda_n^p} T^p s$. Thus each $x_n \in R(T^p)$. Since $R(T^p)$ is closed, the operator T_1 defined in (c) is invertible on $B(R(T^p))$, and let T_1^{-1} denote its inverse. Clearly $Tx_n \rightarrow 0$, hence $T_1^{-1}Tx_n \rightarrow 0$, so $x_n \rightarrow 0$, a contradiction.

(e) By Theorem 1.20 (c), $T \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(T) = 0$. Then, by Remark 1.13 (d), there exists $\varepsilon_1 > 0$ such that for each $|\lambda| < \varepsilon_1$, $\lambda I - T \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$. Now, by (d), there exists $\varepsilon_2 > 0$ such that $p(\lambda I - T) = 0$ for all $0 < |\lambda| < \varepsilon_2$. Let $\varepsilon = \min\{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2\}$; then for each $0 < |\lambda| < \varepsilon$, $\alpha(\lambda I - T) = 0 = \beta(\lambda I - T)$, that is, $\lambda I - T$ is invertible in $B(X)$. Thus 0 is an isolated point of $\sigma(T)$.

We prove that $R(P) = N(T^p)$. By Theorem 1.9 (a), $N(T^p) \subseteq R(P)$. Suppose $N(T^p) \neq R(P)$ and define $U : R(P)/N(T^p) \rightarrow R(P)/N(T^p)$ by

$$U(x + N(T^p)) = Tx + N(T^p), \quad x \in R(P).$$

Observe that $Tx \in R(P)$ since $x \in R(P)$ and P commutes with T . It is clear that U is injective. Assume for the moment that $R(U)$ is closed. Then there exists $c > 0$ such that

$$c\|x + N(T^p)\| \leq \|U(x + N(T^p))\| \quad \text{for all } x \in R(P),$$

which implies that $c^n\|x + N(T^p)\| \leq \|U^n(x + N(T^p))\|$ for every $x \in R(P)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Now observe that

$$U^n(x + N(T^p)) = T^n x + N(T^p),$$

and hence

$$c^n\|x + N(T^p)\| \leq \|T^n x + N(T^p)\| \leq \|T^n x\|$$

for all $x \in R(P)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $x_0 \in R(P)$ with $\|x_0\| = 1$ such that $x_0 \notin N(T^p)$. If $L : R(P) \rightarrow R(P)$ is defined by $L = T|_{R(P)}$, then

$$c^n\|x_0 + N(T^p)\| \leq \|L^n x_0\| \leq \sup_{\|x\|=1} \|L^n x\| = \|L^n\|.$$

Since $\|x_0 + N(T^p)\| \neq 0$, we obtain that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|L^n\|^{1/n} > 0$, which is a contradiction, since by Remark 1.8 (c), $\sigma(L) = \{0\}$. In order to reach the previous contradiction, we need to prove that $R(U)$ is closed. But since

$$R(U) = [R(L) + N(T^p)]/N(T^p),$$

it suffices to show that $[R(L) + N(T^p)]/N(T^p)$ is a complete space. Clearly, the subspace $R(L) = R(T) \cap R(P)$ is closed in X . Now, $\alpha(T) < \infty$ implies that $\dim N(T^p) < \infty$. Hence, $R(L) + N(T^p)$ is a closed subspace of X , and therefore it is complete. Consequently, $[R(L) + N(T^p)]/N(T^p)$ is a complete space.

Now we prove that $N(P) = R(T^p)$. Let $x \in N(P)$. Since $\sigma(T|_{N(P)}) = \sigma(T) \setminus \{0\}$ (see Remark 1.8 (c)), it follows that $T^p|_{N(P)}$ is invertible, and therefore there exists $w \in N(P)$ such that $x = T^p w$. Thus $x \in R(T^p)$. For the reverse inclusion, let $y \in R(T^p)$. Then there exists $z \in X$ such that $y = T^p z$. From what has been shown above, $R(P) = N(T^p)$. Thus $Pz \in N(T^p)$, and consequently $Py = PT^p z = T^p Pz = 0$, that is, $y \in N(P)$. \square

Next, we characterize the points $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$ for which $\lambda I - T$ is a Fredholm operator with finite ascent and descent.

Theorem 1.22. *Let $T \in B(X)$ and $\lambda_0 \in \sigma(T)$. Then $\alpha(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty$ and $p(\lambda_0 I - T) = q(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty$ if and only if λ_0 is an isolated point of the spectrum of T and the range of the projection*

$$P(T, \lambda_0) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_C (z - T)^{-1} dz$$

is finite-dimensional.

Proof. \Leftarrow] Let $P := P(T, \lambda_0)$ and $m = \dim R(P)$. By Theorem 1.9 (b), $R(\lambda_0 I - T)^m = N(P)$ and $N(\lambda_0 I - T)^m = R(P)$. Thus, $X = N(\lambda_0 I - T)^m \oplus R(\lambda_0 I - T)^m$. This implies that

$$\dim (X/R(\lambda_0 I - T)^m) = \dim N(\lambda_0 I - T)^m = \dim R(P) = m < \infty.$$

Hence $(\lambda_0 I - T)^m \in \Phi(X)$, and therefore $\lambda_0 I - T \in \Phi(X)$ (see Remark 1.13 (b)). On the other hand, again using Theorem 1.9, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have

$$N(\lambda_0 I - T)^n \subseteq N(\lambda_0 I - T)^m \quad \text{and} \quad R(\lambda_0 I - T)^m \subseteq R(\lambda_0 I - T)^n.$$

Thus for all $n \geq m$,

$$N(\lambda_0 I - T)^n = N(\lambda_0 I - T)^m \quad \text{and} \quad R(\lambda_0 I - T)^m = R(\lambda_0 I - T)^n.$$

Therefore, $p(\lambda_0 I - T) = q(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty$.

\Rightarrow] By Lemma 1.21 (e), $0 \in \text{iso } \sigma(\lambda_0 I - T)$ and the range of the projection $P(\lambda_0 I - T, 0)$ is $N(\lambda_0 I - T)^p$. Observe that $\lambda_0 \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$ and $P(T, \lambda_0) = P(\lambda_0 I - T, 0)$. Hence the range of $P(T, \lambda_0)$ is finite-dimensional, since $\alpha(\lambda_0 I - T)^p < \infty$. \square

To conclude this section, we establish, in analogy with Remark 1.14 (b), that the ascent and descent of an operator are preserved under compact perturbations that commute with the operator under consideration.

Theorem 1.23. *Let $T \in B(X)$ and $K \in K(X)$ such that $TK = KT$.*

(a) *If $T \in \Phi_+(X)$, then $p(T + K) < \infty$ if and only if $p(T) < \infty$.*

(b) *If $T \in \Phi_-(X)$, then $q(T + K) < \infty$ if and only if $q(T) < \infty$.*

Proof. See [2, Theorem 3.43]. \square

1.5 SVEP

In this section, we introduce the single-valued extension property (SVEP) for an operator $T \in B(X)$. This notion was originally introduced by Dunford [29] and has since played a significant role in local spectral theory; see, for instance, the monograph by Laursen and Neumann [36]. Our focus will be on a localized version of SVEP at a point, a concept introduced by J. Finch [30] and further studied in the recent monograph by Aiena, to which we refer for further details.

An operator $T \in B(X)$ is said to have SVEP at $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ if, for every open neighborhood U_λ of λ , the only analytic function $f : U_\lambda \rightarrow X$ that satisfies

$$(T - \mu)f(\mu) = 0 \quad \text{for all } \mu \in U_\lambda$$

is the function $f \equiv 0$.

We say that T has SVEP if it has SVEP at every $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$. Denote by

$$\Xi(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid T \text{ does not have SVEP at } \lambda\}.$$

Next, we list a series of basic properties of SVEP for an operator $T \in B(X)$, which follow immediately from the above definition.

Remark 1.24. (a) $T \in B(X)$ has SVEP at λ if and only if $\lambda I - T$ has SVEP at 0.

(b) T has SVEP at every point of the resolvent of T .

(c) T has SVEP at every $\lambda \in \partial\sigma(T)$. This is a consequence of the identity theorem for analytic functions. In particular, T has SVEP at every isolated point of the spectrum.

(d) T has SVEP at every λ that is not an accumulation point of $\sigma_p(T)$.

(e) T has SVEP at every λ that is not an accumulation point of $\sigma_{ap}(T)$. This follows directly from the inclusion $\sigma_p(T) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(T)$ and part (d). Since $\sigma_{su}(T) = \sigma_{ap}(T^*)$, by duality it also follows that T^* has SVEP at every λ that is not a limit point of the surjective spectrum $\sigma_{su}(T)$ of T .

(f) If T is quasinilpotent, then T has SVEP; this follows from part (c) and the fact that $\sigma(T) = \{0\}$.

We now characterize the local SVEP at a point. The analytic core and the quasinilpotent part of an operator T play an important role in these characterizations.

The analytic core of T , denoted by $K(T)$, is the set of all $x \in X$ for which there exist a sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X and a real number $\delta > 0$ such that $x = x_0$, $Tx_{n+1} = x_n$, and $\|x_n\| \leq \delta^n \|x\|$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

The quasinilpotent part of T , denoted by $H_0(T)$, is defined by

$$H_0(T) = \{x \in X \mid \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|T^n x\|^{1/n} = 0\}.$$

Some classical properties of these subsets are the following:

Remark 1.25. For $T \in B(X)$, the following hold:

(a) $K(T)$ is a linear subspace of X .

(b) $T(K(T)) = K(T)$.

(c) If Y is a linear subspace of X such that $T(Y) = Y$, then $Y \subseteq K(T)$.

- (d) $N(\lambda I - T) \subseteq K(T)$ for every $\lambda \neq 0$.
- (e) $H_0(T)$ is a T -invariant subspace of X .
- (f) $Tx \in H_0(T)$ if and only if $x \in H_0(T)$.
- (g) $N^\infty(T) \subseteq H_0(T)$.
- (h) $N(\lambda I - T) \cap H_0(T) = \{0\}$ for each $\lambda \neq 0$.

Proposition 1.26. *Let $T \in B(X)$. Then T has SVEP at λ_0 if and only if*

$$N(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap K(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}.$$

Proposition 1.27. *Let $T \in B(X)$ and $\lambda_0 \in \mathbb{C}$. Suppose that one of the following conditions holds:*

- (i) $N(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap R^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (ii) $N(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap R(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (iii) $N^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap K(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (iv) $N^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap R(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (v) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap K(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (vi) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap R^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (vii) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap R(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$.

Then T has SVEP at λ_0 .

Proof. See [2, Chapter 2]. □

Theorem 1.28. *Let $T \in B(X)$. If, for a point $\lambda_0 \in \mathbb{C}$, one of the subspaces $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T)$ or $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap K(\lambda_0 I - T)$ is closed, then T has SVEP at λ_0 .*

Proof. See [2, Theorem 2.31]. □

We now introduce a decomposition property for operators due to Kato [34]. To this end, we say that an operator $T \in B(X)$ is semi-regular if $R(T)$ is closed and T satisfies one of the equivalent inclusions in Proposition 1.17. A generalized Kato decomposition for $T \in B(X)$ (abbreviated as GKD for T) is a pair (M, N) of subspaces of X , closed and T -invariant, such that $X = M \oplus N$ and the restrictions $T|_M$ and $T|_N$ are, respectively, semi-regular and quasinilpotent.

An operator $T \in B(X)$ is said to be of Kato type if there exists a GKD (M, N) for T such that $T|_N$ is nilpotent.

An operator is said to be essentially semi-regular if there exists a GKD (M, N) such that N is finite-dimensional. Note that if T is essentially semi-regular, then $T|_N$ is nilpotent, since

every quasinilpotent operator on a finite-dimensional space is nilpotent. Therefore, we have the following implications:

$$T \text{ is semi-regular} \Rightarrow T \text{ is essentially semi-regular} \Rightarrow T \text{ is of Kato type.}$$

Theorem 1.29. *If $T \in B(X)$ is a semi-Fredholm operator, then T is essentially semi-regular.*

Proof. See [2, Theorem 1.62]. □

We now describe SVEP for operators that admit a GKD.

Theorem 1.30. *Suppose that $\lambda_0 I - T \in B(X)$ is of Kato type. Let (M, N) be the GKD for $\lambda_0 I - T$. Then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (a) T has SVEP at λ_0 ;
- (b) $T|_M$ has SVEP at λ_0 ;
- (c) $(\lambda_0 I - T)|_M$ is injective;
- (d) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) = N$;
- (e) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T)$ is closed;
- (f) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap K(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (g) $H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap K(\lambda_0 I - T)$ is closed;
- (h) $p(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty$;
- (i) $N^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) \cap R^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) = \{0\}$;
- (j) λ_0 is not an accumulation point of $\sigma_{ap}(T)$.

Proof. See [2, Chapter 3]. □

The following statements concern SVEP for the dual and can be viewed as dual versions of the previously studied conditions.

Theorem 1.31. *Suppose that $\lambda_0 I - T \in B(X)$ is of Kato type. Let (M, N) be the GKD for $\lambda_0 I - T$. Then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (a) T^* has SVEP at λ_0 ;
- (b) $T^*|_{N^\perp}$ has SVEP at λ_0 ;
- (c) $(\lambda_0 I - T)|_M$ is surjective;
- (d) $K(\lambda_0 I - T) = M$;
- (e) $X = H_0(\lambda_0 I - T) + K(\lambda_0 I - T)$;

- (f) $q(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty$;
- (g) $X = N^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T) + R^\infty(\lambda_0 I - T)$;
- (h) λ_0 is not an accumulation point of $\sigma_{su}(T)$.

Proof. See [2, Chapter 3]. □

For an operator $\lambda_0 I - T$ that is essentially regular, the previous theorem tells us that

$$T^* \text{ has SVEP at } \lambda_0 \Rightarrow \lambda_0 I - T \in \Phi_-(X),$$

since T^* having SVEP at λ_0 implies that $\dim X/K(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty$. Now, by Remark 1.25 (b), $K(\lambda_0 I - T) \subseteq R(\lambda_0 I - T)$, from which it follows that

$$\beta(\lambda_0 I - T) = \dim X/R(\lambda_0 I - T) \leq \dim X/K(\lambda_0 I - T) < \infty.$$

Thus $\lambda_0 I - T \in \Phi_-(X)$.

Now observe that if $\lambda_0 I - T \in \Phi_\pm(X)$, then $\lambda_0 I - T$ is essentially semi-regular (see Theorem 1.29). Thus, the preceding characterizations remain valid for describing the SVEP of an operator T (resp. T^*) at a point λ_0 , in the case where $\lambda_0 I - T \in \Phi_\pm(X)$. Moreover, from the previous results it follows that for $\lambda_0 I - T \in \Phi_\pm(X)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T \text{ has SVEP at } \lambda_0 &\Rightarrow i(\lambda_0 I - T) \leq 0; \\ T^* \text{ has SVEP at } \lambda_0 &\Rightarrow i(\lambda_0 I - T) \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

To conclude the section, we present some classes of operators that have the SVEP property. Let H be a Hilbert space. An operator $T \in B(H)$ is said to be normal if $T^*T = TT^*$; it is hyponormal if $T^*T \leq TT^*$; it is p -hyponormal if $(T^*T)^p \leq (TT^*)^p$; it is M -hyponormal if there exists a number $M \geq 1$ such that $|\bar{\lambda} - T^*|^2 \leq M|\lambda - T|^2$ for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$; it is (p, q) -quasihyponormal if $T^{*k}(|T|^{2p} - |T^*|^{2p})T^k \geq 0$ where $0 < p \leq 1$ and k is a positive integer; it is of class A if $|T|^2 \leq |T^2|$; it is $*$ -paranormal if $\|T^*x\|^2 \leq \|T^2x\|^2$ for every unit vector $x \in H$, and it is paranormal if $\|Tx\|^2 \leq \|T^2x\|^2$ for every unit vector $x \in H$.

The following inclusions hold:

$$\text{normal} \subseteq \text{hyponormal} \subseteq p\text{-hyponormal} \subseteq \text{class } A \subseteq \text{paranormal}.$$

Also,

$$p\text{-hyponormal} \subseteq (p, q)\text{-quasihyponormal}.$$

The classes M -hyponormal and $*$ -paranormal are independent of the classes (p, q) -quasihyponormal and paranormal. Any operator belonging to these classes has the single-valued extension property (SVEP). See [25].

1.6 Operator Matrices

Let X and Y be Banach spaces over the complex field \mathbb{C} . Recall that the direct sum of X and Y , denoted by $X \oplus Y$, is the set of ordered pairs (x, y) with $x \in X$ and $y \in Y$, where the addition and scalar multiplication are defined by

$$(x_1, y_1) + (x_2, y_2) = (x_1 + x_2, y_1 + y_2),$$

$$\alpha(x, y) = (\alpha x, \alpha y).$$

The functions $\|\cdot\|_p : X \oplus Y \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ (for each real number $p \geq 1$) and $\|\cdot\|_\infty : X \oplus Y \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by

$$\|(x, y)\|_p = \left(\|x\|_X^p + \|y\|_Y^p\right)^{1/p} \quad \text{and} \quad \|(x, y)\|_\infty = \max\{\|x\|_X, \|y\|_Y\}$$

are norms on $X \oplus Y$ and generate the same topology. Moreover, $X \oplus Y$ endowed with any of these norms is a Banach space if and only if X and Y are Banach spaces. Thus, when referring to the norm on the direct sum $X \oplus Y$, we mean either $\|\cdot\|_p$ or $\|\cdot\|_\infty$, and we will simply denote it by $\|\cdot\|$.

Let \mathcal{M} denote the family of matrices of bounded linear operators:

$$\mathcal{M} = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} : A \in B(X), B \in B(Y, X), C \in B(X, Y), D \in B(Y) \right\}.$$

The space \mathcal{M} , equipped with the usual matrix operations:

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 \\ C_1 & D_1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} A_2 & B_2 \\ C_2 & D_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_1 + A_2 & B_1 + B_2 \\ C_1 + C_2 & D_1 + D_2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\alpha \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha A & \alpha B \\ \alpha C & \alpha D \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 \\ C_1 & D_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} A_2 & B_2 \\ C_2 & D_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_1 A_2 + B_1 C_2 & A_1 B_2 + B_1 D_2 \\ C_1 A_2 + D_1 C_2 & C_1 B_2 + D_1 D_2 \end{pmatrix},$$

is an algebra.

Now, let $\begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{M}$ and define $T \in B(X \oplus Y)$ by

$$T(x, y) = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}. \tag{1.5}$$

This operator is commonly called an operator matrix. Observe that there is a bijective

correspondence between \mathcal{M} and $B(X \oplus Y)$. Indeed, define $\Phi : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow B(X \oplus Y)$ by

$$\Phi \left(\begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \right) = T,$$

where T is defined as in (1.5). It is clear that Φ is bijective and that for each $M, N \in \mathcal{M}$, $\Phi(MN) = \Phi(M)\Phi(N)$. Thus, Φ is an isomorphism between the algebras \mathcal{M} and $B(X \oplus Y)$. Therefore, the operator $T \in B(X \oplus Y)$ defined in (1.5) can be identified with the matrix

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix},$$

and we usually write

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix}.$$

Note that, since Φ is a homomorphism, T is invertible in $B(X \oplus Y)$ if and only if

$$\begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix}$$

is invertible in \mathcal{M} .

Moreover, if we equip the algebra \mathcal{M} with the norm

$$\left\| \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \right\| = \inf \left\{ \alpha > 0 : \left\| \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ C & D \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \right\| \leq \alpha \|(x, y)\| \text{ for all } (x, y) \in X \oplus Y \right\},$$

then \mathcal{M} is a Banach algebra. Clearly, for each $M \in \mathcal{M}$, we have $\|M\| = \|\Phi(M)\|$.

Example 1.32. If $T \in B(H)$ is (p, k) -quasihyponormal, then T admits the following representation:

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} T_1 & T_2 \\ 0 & T_3 \end{pmatrix},$$

where T_1 is p -hyponormal on $\overline{R(T^k)}$ and $T_3^k = 0$.

Chapter 2

Basic Spectra in Fredholm Theory and Browder-Type Theorems

In this chapter, we describe several spectral subsets associated with an operator $T \in B(X)$, where X is a Banach space, motivated by the classes of operators introduced in the previous chapter, including Fredholm operators, Fredholm operators of index 0, and operators with finite ascent and descent. In the second part, we examine Browder's and a -Browder's theorems in relation to the concept of SVEP.

2.1 Fredholm, Weyl, and Browder Spectra

Recall that an operator $T \in B(X)$ is Fredholm, $T \in \Phi(X)$, if $R(T)$ is closed, $\alpha(T) < \infty$ and $\beta(T) < \infty$. The Fredholm spectrum of an operator $T \in B(X)$ is defined by

$$\sigma_F(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \text{ is not Fredholm}\}.$$

There exists a well-established connection between the Calkin algebra $C(X)$ and the class of Fredholm operators; see Corollary 1.16. More precisely, the Fredholm spectrum of an operator T coincides with the set

$$\{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - \pi(T) \text{ is not invertible in } C(X)\}.$$

This set is known as the essential spectrum of T and is denoted by $\sigma_e(T)$. In particular, $\sigma_e(T) = \sigma(\pi(T))$. Therefore, $\sigma_F(T)$, which agrees with $\sigma_e(T)$, is a nonempty compact subset of \mathbb{C} .

Similarly, we define the semi-Fredholm spectrum of $T \in B(X)$ by

$$\sigma_{sF}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \notin \Phi_{\pm}(X)\}.$$

By Remark 1.13 (d), we know that $\Phi_{\pm}(X)$ is an open subset of $B(X)$; thus $\sigma_{sF}(T)$ is a closed subset of \mathbb{C} . However, $\sigma_{sF}(T)$ may be empty.

We now introduce the classes of semi-Browder, Browder, and Weyl operators. The class

of upper semi-Browder operators, denoted by $B_+(X)$, is defined by

$$B_+(X) = \{T \in \Phi_+(X) \mid p(T) < \infty\},$$

and the class of lower semi-Browder operators, denoted by $B_-(X)$, by

$$B_-(X) = \{T \in \Phi_-(X) \mid q(T) < \infty\}.$$

The intersection $B_+(X) \cap B_-(X)$ defines the class of Browder operators, also known in the literature as Riesz–Schauder operators. Note that by Theorem 1.20, if $T \in B_+(X)$, then $i(T) \leq 0$, whereas if $T \in B_-(X)$, then $i(T) \geq 0$.

The class of Weyl operators, denoted by $W(X)$, is defined by

$$W(X) = \{T \in \Phi(X) \mid i(T) = 0\}.$$

These classes of operators naturally motivate the definition of certain spectra associated with each of them. Indeed, for $T \in B(X)$, the sets

$$\sigma_{ub}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \notin B_+(X)\},$$

$$\sigma_{lb}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \notin B_-(X)\},$$

$$\sigma_b(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \notin B_+(X) \cap B_-(X)\},$$

$$\sigma_w(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \notin W(X)\},$$

define, respectively, the upper semi-Browder, lower semi-Browder, Browder, and Weyl spectra. Clearly,

$$\sigma_b(T) = \sigma_{ub}(T) \cup \sigma_{lb}(T).$$

By Remark 1.13 (c) and the equalities given in (1.4), we have

$$\sigma_{ub}(T) = \sigma_{lb}(T^*) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_{lb}(T) = \sigma_{ub}(T^*).$$

Hence,

$$\sigma_b(T) = \sigma_b(T^*).$$

Using again Remark 1.13 (c), we also have

$$\sigma_w(T) = \sigma_w(T^*).$$

On the other hand, for each $T \in B(X)$,

$$\sigma_e(T) = \sigma_F(T) \subseteq \sigma_w(T) \subseteq \sigma_b(T) \subseteq \sigma(T).$$

Theorem 2.1. *Let $T \in B(X)$. Then*

(a)

$$\sigma_{ub}(T) = \bigcap_{\substack{K \in K(X) \\ KT=TK}} \sigma_{ap}(T + K);$$

(b)

$$\sigma_{lb}(T) = \bigcap_{\substack{K \in K(X) \\ KT=TK}} \sigma_{su}(T + K);$$

(c)

$$\sigma_b(T) = \bigcap_{\substack{K \in K(X) \\ KT=TK}} \sigma(T + K).$$

Proof. See [2, Chapter 3]. □

Similarly, by Remark 1.14 (b), we obtain the following characterization for the Weyl spectrum.

Theorem 2.2. *If $T \in B(X)$, then*

$$\sigma_w(T) = \bigcap_{K \in K(X)} \sigma(T + K).$$

For $T \in B(X)$, the Weyl approximate point spectrum of T , denoted by $\sigma_{wa}(T)$, is given by

$$\sigma_{wa}(T) = \bigcap_{K \in K(X)} \sigma_{ap}(T + K),$$

while the Weyl surjective spectrum of T , denoted by $\sigma_{ws}(T)$, is defined by

$$\sigma_{ws}(T) = \bigcap_{K \in K(X)} \sigma_{su}(T + K).$$

The following theorem describes the approximate point and surjective Weyl spectra in terms of semi-Fredholm operators and the notion of the index of an operator.

Theorem 2.3. *For an operator $T \in B(X)$, the following hold:*

- (a) $\sigma_{wa}(T) \subseteq \sigma_{ub}(T)$ and $\sigma_{ws}(T) \subseteq \sigma_{lb}(T)$;
- (b) $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$ if and only if $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - T) \leq 0$;
- (c) $\lambda \notin \sigma_{ws}(T)$ if and only if $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_-(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - T) \geq 0$;
- (d) $\sigma_{wa}(T) = \sigma_{ws}(T^*)$ and $\sigma_{ws}(T) = \sigma_{wa}(T^*)$;
- (e) $\sigma_w(T) = \sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \sigma_{ws}(T)$.

Proof. See [2, Chapter 3]. □

2.2 Browder-Type Theorems

In this section, we introduce the Browder and a -Browder theorems for bounded linear operators on Banach spaces. These results impose a specific structure on the spectrum of an operator. More precisely, an operator T satisfies Browder's theorem if the set of points λ in the spectrum for which $\lambda I - T$ is a Weyl operator coincides with the set of eigenvalues that are isolated points of the spectrum with finite algebraic multiplicity. This property holds, in particular, for all self-adjoint operators on Hilbert spaces, although the class of operators satisfying these theorems is much wider. In this chapter, we investigate the interplay between these theorems and the single-valued extension property (SVEP).

For a subset A of \mathbb{C} , we denote by $\text{acc } A$ the set of its accumulation points.

Proposition 2.4. *For $T \in B(X)$, the following hold:*

- (a) $\sigma_b(T) = \sigma_w(T) \cup \text{acc } \sigma(T)$;
- (b) $\sigma_{ub}(T) = \sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \text{acc } \sigma_{ap}(T)$.

Proof. (a) Clearly, $\sigma_w(T) \cup \text{acc } \sigma(T) \subseteq \sigma_b(T)$; see Theorem 1.22. Now suppose that there exists $\lambda \in \sigma_b(T) \setminus (\sigma_w(T) \cup \text{acc } \sigma(T))$. Then $\lambda I - T \in \Phi(X)$, $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$, and $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$. By Remark 1.24 (c), T has SVEP at λ . Thus, by Theorem 1.30, $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Moreover, by Theorem 1.20 (d), $p(\lambda I - T) = q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Hence, $\lambda I - T$ is a Browder operator, which is a contradiction.

(b) Let $\lambda \in \sigma_{ub}(T) \setminus (\sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \text{acc } \sigma_{ap}(T))$. Then $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and λ is not an accumulation point of $\sigma_{ap}(T)$. Thus, by Theorem 1.30 (j) \Rightarrow (h), $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$, and therefore $\lambda I - T \in B_+(X)$, which is a contradiction.

Using again Theorem 1.30, we see that $\sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \text{acc } \sigma_{ap}(T) \subseteq \sigma_{ub}(T)$. □

We say that an operator $T \in B(X)$ satisfies Browder's theorem if

$$\sigma_w(T) = \sigma_b(T),$$

or equivalently, by Proposition 2.4 (a), if

$$\text{acc } \sigma(T) \subseteq \sigma_w(T).$$

Consider the set

$$\Delta(T) := \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T).$$

Clearly, if $\lambda \in \Delta(T)$, then $\lambda I - T \in W(X)$, and since $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$, it follows that $\alpha(\lambda I - T) = \beta(\lambda I - T) > 0$. Thus, we can express the set $\Delta(T)$ as

$$\Delta(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \in W(X), 0 < \alpha(\lambda I - T)\}.$$

The points of $\Delta(T)$ are known as generalized Riesz points. By Theorem 1.22, it is easy to see that

$$\pi_0(T) \subseteq \Delta(T).$$

The following theorem characterizes operators T that satisfy Browder's theorem. Many of these conditions are well known and appear in various articles; see, for example, [2, 3, 4, 10, 9, 21, 25, 26, 39].

Theorem 2.5. *For an operator $T \in B(X)$, the following statements are equivalent:*

- (a) $\pi_0(T) = \Delta(T)$;
- (b) $\pi(T) = \sigma_w(T) \cup \text{iso } \sigma(T)$;
- (c) T satisfies Browder's theorem;
- (d) T^* satisfies Browder's theorem;
- (e) $q(\lambda I - T^*) < \infty$ for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (f) $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (g) T has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (h) T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (i) $\dim H_0(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for every $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (j) $H_0(\lambda I - T)$ is closed for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (k) $\dim X/K(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for every $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$;
- (l) Each $\lambda \in \Delta(T)$ is an isolated point of $\sigma(T)$.

An approximation to Browder's theorem is given by the a -Browder theorem. Indeed, an operator $T \in B(X)$ is said to satisfy the a -Browder theorem if

$$\sigma_{wa}(T) = \sigma_{ub}(T),$$

or equivalently, by Proposition 2.4 (b), if

$$\text{acc } \sigma_{ap}(T) \subseteq \sigma_{wa}(T).$$

The following theorem is analogous to Theorem 2.5 for operators that satisfy the a -Browder theorem. Let

$$\Delta_a(T) = \sigma_{ap}(T) \setminus \sigma_{wa}(T).$$

Theorem 2.6. *For $T \in B(X)$, the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (a) $\sigma_{ap}(T) \setminus \sigma_{wa}(T) = \{\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma_{ap}(T) \mid \lambda I - T \in \Phi_+(X), p(\lambda I - T) < \infty\}$;
- (b) T satisfies the a -Browder theorem;
- (c) $\sigma_{ap}(T) = \sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \text{iso } \sigma_{ap}(T)$;

- (d) $\sigma_{ub}(T) = \sigma_{wa}(T)$;
- (e) $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$;
- (f) $\dim H_0(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$;
- (g) $H_0(\lambda I - T)$ is closed for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$;
- (h) Each $\lambda \in \Delta_a(T)$ is an isolated point of $\sigma_{ap}(T)$.

Since $\sigma_{wa}(T) \subseteq \sigma_w(T)$, from the previous theorem and Theorem 2.5 it follows immediately that

a -Browder theorem \Rightarrow Browder theorem.

Observe that: “ T satisfies the a -Browder theorem” does not imply that “ T^* satisfies the a -Browder theorem”. On the other hand, the following characterizations of the a -Browder theorem are given for T and T^* .

Theorem 2.7. *For $T \in B(X)$, the following hold:*

- (a) T satisfies the a -Browder theorem if and only if T has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$.
- (b) T^* satisfies the a -Browder theorem if and only if T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{ws}(T)$.
- (c) If T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$, then T satisfies the a -Browder theorem.
- (d) If T has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{ws}(T)$, then T^* satisfies the a -Browder theorem.

From this, we conclude that a necessary and sufficient condition for T to satisfy the a -Browder theorem is that either T or T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$.

Chapter 3

Left–Right Essential Spectrum

In this chapter we introduce a part of the spectrum known as the left–right essential spectrum, which will be very useful in the next chapter, together with some of its properties. The results presented in this part are generalizations, to Banach spaces, of some results established in Section 1 of [13].

Recall that $G_l(Y)$ and $G_r(Y)$ denote, respectively, the sets of elements that are left invertible in Y and those that are right invertible in Y . We define the left essential spectrum of $T \in B(X)$, denoted by $\sigma_{le}(T)$, as

$$\sigma_{le}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - \pi(T) \notin G_l(C(X))\},$$

and the right essential spectrum of T , $\sigma_{re}(T)$, by

$$\sigma_{re}(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - \pi(T) \notin G_r(C(X))\}.$$

Clearly, $\sigma_{le}(T)$ and $\sigma_{re}(T)$ are closed subsets of \mathbb{C} , because $G_l(C(X))$ and $G_r(C(X))$ are open subsets of $C(X)$. Also, from the definition of these sets, we have

$$\sigma_e(T) = \sigma_{le}(T) \cup \sigma_{re}(T).$$

The left–right essential spectrum of $T \in B(X)$, denoted by $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, is the intersection of $\sigma_{le}(T)$ and $\sigma_{re}(T)$, that is,

$$\sigma_{lre}(T) = \sigma_{le}(T) \cap \sigma_{re}(T).$$

We know that if $\lambda I - \pi(T)$ is left or right invertible, then $\lambda I - T$ is semi-Fredholm; see Theorem 1.15. Thus,

$$\sigma_{sF}(T) \subseteq \sigma_{lre}(T).$$

The reverse inclusion also holds in Hilbert spaces, since every closed subspace is complemented. Therefore, in Hilbert spaces,

$$\sigma_{sF}(T) = \sigma_{lre}(T).$$

However, in Banach spaces the inclusion $\sigma_{lre}(T) \subseteq \sigma_{sF}(T)$ does not always hold, as shown by the following example:

Example 3.1. Consider the Banach space ℓ^p where $p \in (2, \infty)$. Since $p \neq 2$, there exists a closed linear subspace E of ℓ^p for which there is no bounded projection from ℓ^p onto E . Let $\ell^p \oplus \ell^p$ be the Banach space endowed with the norm $\|(x, y)\| = \|x\| + \|y\|$. Clearly, $E \oplus \ell^p$ is a closed subspace of $\ell^p \oplus \ell^p$. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, let $e_k = (\delta_{kj})_{j \in \mathbb{N}}$, where $\delta_{kj} = 1$ if $j = k$ and $\delta_{kj} = 0$ otherwise. Consider the operator $T : \ell^p \rightarrow \ell^p \oplus \ell^p$ defined by

$$T(\{x_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}) = \left(\sum_{k \in \mathbb{N}} x_{2k} e_k, \sum_{k \in \mathbb{N}} x_{2k-1} e_k \right).$$

Then T is a bounded linear and invertible operator. Now define $A : E \oplus \ell^p \rightarrow E \oplus \ell^p$ by

$$A(x, y) = (0, T^{-1}(x, y)), \quad (x, y) \in E \oplus \ell^p.$$

It is not difficult to show that A is a bounded linear operator, and moreover it satisfies $N(A) = \{(0, 0)\}$ and $R(A) = \{0\} \oplus T^{-1}(E \oplus \ell^p) = \overline{R(A)}$. Thus, A is a semi-Fredholm operator, and consequently

$$0 \notin \sigma_{sF}(A).$$

However, $0 \in \sigma_{le}(A) \cap \sigma_{re}(A)$. Indeed, if $R(A)$ is not complemented in $E \oplus \ell^p$, then by Theorem 1.15 (a), $0 \in \sigma_{le}(A)$. On the other hand, it is also true that $\beta(A) = \infty$, and this implies (Theorem 1.15 (b)) that $0 \in \sigma_{re}(A)$. Thus, it suffices to show that $R(A)$ is not complemented in $E \oplus \ell^p$, or equivalently, that there does not exist a bounded projection from $E \oplus \ell^p$ onto $R(A)$. Suppose that there exists a projection $P \in B(E \oplus \ell^p)$ such that

$$R(P) = R(A) = \{0\} \oplus T^{-1}(E \oplus \ell^p).$$

For each $n = 1, 2$, define bounded operators $P_n : \ell^p \oplus \ell^p \rightarrow \ell^p$ and $J_n : \ell^p \rightarrow \ell^p \oplus \ell^p$ by

$$P_n(x_1, x_2) = x_n, \quad (x_1, x_2) \in \ell^p \oplus \ell^p,$$

and

$$J_n(x) = (\delta_{1n}x, \delta_{2n}x), \quad x \in \ell^p.$$

Now define $Q = P_1 T P_2 P J_2 T^{-1} J_1$. Then $Q \in B(\ell^p)$ and

$$Q(\ell^p) \subseteq P_1 T P_2 P(E \oplus \ell^p) = P_1 T P_2(\{0\} \oplus T^{-1}(E \oplus \ell^p)) = P_1 T(T^{-1}(E \oplus \ell^p)) = P_1(E \oplus \ell^p) = E.$$

Moreover, for each $x \in E$,

$$\begin{aligned}
Qx &= P_1TP_2PJ_2T^{-1}J_1x \\
&= P_1TP_2PJ_2T^{-1}(x, 0) \\
&= P_1TP_2P(0, T^{-1}(x, 0)) \\
&= P_1TP_2(0, T^{-1}(x, 0)) \\
&= P_1TT^{-1}(x, 0) \\
&= P_1(x, 0) = x.
\end{aligned}$$

Consequently, Q is a bounded projection from ℓ^p onto E , which is a contradiction. Therefore, there does not exist a bounded projection from $E \oplus \ell^p$ onto $R(A)$.

Next, we present subsets of special interest for this chapter and the next one. For $T \in B(X)$, define

$$\begin{aligned}
\rho_{sF}(T) &= \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \in \Phi_{\pm}(X)\}, \\
\rho_{sF}^+(T) &= \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}(T) \mid i(\lambda I - T) > 0\}, \\
\rho_{sF}^-(T) &= \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}(T) \mid i(\lambda I - T) < 0\}, \\
\rho_{sF}^{+\infty}(T) &= \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}(T) \mid i(\lambda I - T) = \infty\},
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T) = \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}(T) \mid i(\lambda I - T) = -\infty\}.$$

Set

$$\rho_{sF}^{\pm\infty}(T) = \rho_{sF}^{+\infty}(T) \cup \rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T) \quad \text{and} \quad \rho_{sF}^{\pm}(T) = \rho_{sF}^+(T) \cup \rho_{sF}^-(T).$$

Since $\Phi_{\pm}(X)$ is an open subset of $B(X)$ and $i : B(X) \rightarrow \mathbb{Z} \cup \{\pm\infty\}$ is a continuous function (see Remark 1.13 (d)), it follows that $\rho_{sF}(T)$, $\rho_{sF}^+(T)$, $\rho_{sF}^-(T)$, $\rho_{sF}^{+\infty}(T)$, $\rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T)$, and $\rho_{sF}^{\pm\infty}(T)$ are open subsets of \mathbb{C} . We now restrict the previous subsets in the following way: for $T \in B(X)$, define

$$\begin{aligned}
\phi_+(T) &= \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}^+(T) \mid N(\lambda I - T) \text{ is complemented in } X\}, \\
\phi_{+\infty}(T) &= \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}^{+\infty}(T) \mid N(\lambda I - T) \text{ is complemented in } X\}, \\
\phi_-(T) &= \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}^-(T) \mid R(\lambda I - T) \text{ is complemented in } X\},
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\phi_{-\infty}(T) = \{\lambda \in \rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T) \mid R(\lambda I - T) \text{ is complemented in } X\}.$$

Set

$$\phi_{\pm\infty}(T) = \phi_{+\infty}(T) \cup \phi_{-\infty}(T).$$

Observe that in Hilbert spaces one has

$$\phi_+(T) = \rho_{sF}^+(T), \quad \phi_{+\infty}(T) = \rho_{sF}^{+\infty}(T), \quad \phi_-(T) = \rho_{sF}^-(T), \quad \phi_{-\infty}(T) = \rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T).$$

Proposition 3.2. *For $T \in B(X)$, the subsets $\phi_+(T)$, $\phi_-(T)$, $\phi_{+\infty}(T)$, and $\phi_{-\infty}(T)$ are open in \mathbb{C} .*

Proof. By Theorem 1.15, we have the equality

$$\phi_+(T) = \rho_{sF}^+(T) \cap \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \in \pi^{-1}(G_r(C(X)))\}.$$

Now, the set on the right-hand side of the intersection is open, since $G_r(C(X))$ is open and π is continuous. Hence $\phi_+(T)$ is open in \mathbb{C} . \square

Lemma 3.3. *If $T \in B(X)$, then:*

$$(a) \quad \sigma_e(T) = \sigma_{sF}(T) \cup \rho_{sF}^{\pm\infty}(T);$$

$$(b) \quad \sigma_e(T) = \sigma_{lre}(T) \cup \phi_{\pm\infty}(T);$$

$$(c) \quad \partial\sigma_e(T) \subseteq \sigma_{sF}(T).$$

Proof. (a) It is trivial.

(b) Let $\lambda \in \sigma_e(T)$. If $\lambda \in \sigma_{le}(T)$ and $\lambda \in \sigma_{re}(T)$, then $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T)$. Suppose that $\lambda I - \pi(T)$ is left invertible in $C(X)$. Then, by Theorem 1.15 (a), $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $R(\lambda I - T)$ is complemented in X . Since $\lambda \in \sigma_e(T)$, we have $\beta(\lambda I - T) = \infty$, hence $i(\lambda I - T) = -\infty$. Consequently, $\lambda \in \phi_{-\infty}(T)$.

Similarly, when $\lambda I - \pi(T)$ is right invertible, we obtain $\lambda \in \phi_{+\infty}(T)$. Therefore,

$$\sigma_e(T) \subseteq \sigma_{lre}(T) \cup \Omega^{\pm\infty}(T).$$

The reverse inclusion is immediate.

(c) Since $\rho_{sF}^{\pm\infty}(T)$ is an open set, we have $\rho_{sF}^{\pm\infty}(T) \subseteq \sigma_e(T)^\circ$, and this implies that

$$\partial\sigma_e(T) = \sigma_e(T) \setminus \sigma_e(T)^\circ \subseteq \sigma_e(T) \setminus \rho_{sF}^{\pm\infty}(T).$$

Then, by part (a), $\partial\sigma_e(T) \subseteq \sigma_{sF}(T)$. Clearly, from part (b) of the previous lemma, if for every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$ we have $i(\lambda I - T) \geq 0$, then

$$\sigma_e(T) = \sigma_{lre}(T) \cup \phi_{+\infty}(T).$$

\square

3.1 Connectivity Relations between the Left–Right Essential Spectrum and the Essential Spectrum

In this part, we establish a theorem that shows certain connectivity relations between $\sigma_{lre}(T)$ and $\sigma_e(T)$.

Lemma 3.4. *Let $T \in B(X)$. If C is a component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$ such that*

$$C \cap \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} = \emptyset,$$

then C is a component of $\sigma_e(T)$.

Proof. Let C be a component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$ such that $C \cap \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} = \emptyset$. Then there exists $\varepsilon_1 > 0$ such that

$$(C)_{\varepsilon_1} \cap \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} = \emptyset.$$

By Lemma 3.3 (b),

$$\sigma_e(T) = \sigma_{lre}(T) \cup \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)}.$$

Let D be a component of $\sigma_e(T)$ such that $C \subseteq D$. Then

$$D = (\sigma_{lre}(T) \cap D) \cup (\overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} \cap D).$$

Set $K = \sigma_{lre}(T) \cap D$ and show that for every $\varepsilon > 0$, $K \subseteq (C)_\varepsilon$. Suppose the contrary, that there exists $\varepsilon_2 > 0$ such that $K \not\subseteq (C)_{\varepsilon_2}$. Let $r = \min\{\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2\}$; then

$$(C)_r \cap \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} = \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad K \setminus (C)_r \neq \emptyset.$$

Define

$$\mathcal{U} = \{K \setminus A : A \text{ is open and closed in } K \text{ with } C \subseteq A\}.$$

Since quasi-components and components coincide for compact Hausdorff spaces, it follows that \mathcal{U} is an open cover of $K \setminus (C)_r$. By the compactness of $K \setminus (C)_r$, there exist open and closed sets A_1, \dots, A_n in K with $C \subseteq A_i$ for all i , such that

$$K \setminus (C)_r \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^n (K \setminus A_i) = K \setminus \bigcap_{i=1}^n A_i.$$

Set $A_0 = \bigcap_{i=1}^n A_i$ and $B_0 = K \setminus A_0$. Then A_0 and B_0 are compact sets such that

$$K = A_0 \cup B_0, \quad A_0 \cap B_0 = \emptyset,$$

with $C \subseteq A_0 \subseteq (C)_r$, $A_0 \neq \emptyset$, and by the previous conditions, $B_0 \neq \emptyset$. Therefore,

$$D = A_0 \cup \left(B_0 \cup (\overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} \cap D) \right),$$

and

$$A_0 \cap \left(B_0 \cup (\overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} \cap D) \right) = \emptyset.$$

This implies that D is disconnected, which is a contradiction. Thus, for every $\varepsilon > 0$, we have $C \subseteq K \subseteq (C)_\varepsilon$. Hence K is connected, and so $K = C$.

Consequently,

$$D = C \cup (\overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} \cap D).$$

Since D is connected, $C \neq \emptyset$, and

$$C \cap (\overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} \cap D) = \emptyset,$$

it follows that $\overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} \cap D = \emptyset$. Therefore $D = C$. \square

Observe that, in the previous theorem, the set $\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)$ can be replaced by $\phi_{+\infty}(T)$ whenever $i(\lambda I - T) \geq 0$ for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. Indeed:

Lemma 3.5. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be such that $i(\lambda I - T) \geq 0$ for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. If C is a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$ and $C \cap \overline{\phi_{+\infty}(T)} = \emptyset$, then C is a connected component of $\sigma_e(T)$.*

Similarly, if $i(\lambda I - T) \leq 0$ for all $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$, then the set $\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)$ can be replaced by $\phi_{-\infty}(T)$.

Chapter 4

Continuity of the Spectrum on Bounded Operators

The spectrum can be regarded as a function σ that assigns to each operator $T \in B(X)$ its spectrum $\sigma(T)$. In this chapter, we study the continuity of the spectrum and some of its parts, where $B(X)$ is equipped with the norm topology, and the codomain is endowed with the Hausdorff metric. Several authors have studied these topics; among them we mention: Newburgh [37], Conway and Morrel [13, 14], Laura Burlando [11], S. V. Djordjević [19, 20], B. P. Duggal, I. H. Jeon and I. H. Kim [28], among others.

The chapter is organized as follows. In the first section we study the convergence with the Hausdorff metric of a sequence of nonempty compact subsets. In the second section, we characterize the continuity of the spectrum and its parts in terms of upper and lower limits. We also prove that the spectrum function is upper semicontinuous. In the third part, we present conditions for the continuity of the spectrum and some of its parts, especially for the continuity of the approximate point spectrum. In the fourth section, we show that if the spectrum function is continuous at an operator T , then T satisfies Browder's theorem; a similar relation holds for the approximate point spectrum. Finally, in the last section, we study the continuity of the spectrum of $T + K$, where K is a compact operator.

4.1 Convergence with the Hausdorff Metric

Throughout this section, E will denote a metric space. In the classical literature on the Hausdorff metric, it is known that there exists a characterization of convergence with respect to the Hausdorff metric through the concepts of lower and upper limits of a sequence of subsets of E . In this section, conditions are given under which this characterization holds without requiring the total space E to be compact.

Definition 4.1. Let $A \subseteq E$ and $\epsilon > 0$. The ϵ -neighborhood (or ϵ -cloud) of A is defined as

$$(A)_\epsilon = \{x \in E : d(x, A) < \epsilon\},$$

where $d(x, A) = \inf\{d(x, y) : y \in A\}$ is the distance from x to A .

Definition 4.2. Let \mathcal{S} be the collection of nonempty and compact subsets of E . The function $h : \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{S} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\}$ defined by

$$h(A, B) = \inf\{\epsilon > 0 : A \subseteq (B)_\epsilon \text{ and } B \subseteq (A)_\epsilon\},$$

for each $A, B \in \mathcal{S}$, is a metric on \mathcal{S} . This metric is commonly known as the Hausdorff metric.

It is of interest to understand how convergence behaves in \mathcal{S} under the Hausdorff metric. To this end, directly verifying whether a sequence $\{E_n\}$ in \mathcal{S} converges to $E \in \mathcal{S}$ is complicated, so it is convenient to check convergence in a simpler way. This is achieved through the concepts of upper and lower limits of a sequence of elements in \mathcal{S} .

Definition 4.3. Let $\{E_n\}$ be a sequence of subsets in E . The lower and upper limits of $\{E_n\}$ are defined as follows:

- $\liminf E_n = \{x \in E : \text{for every } \epsilon > 0, \text{ there exists } n_0 \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } B_\epsilon(x) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset \text{ for all } n \geq n_0\}$.
- $\limsup E_n = \{x \in E : \text{for every } \epsilon > 0, \text{ there exists an infinite set } J \subseteq \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } B_\epsilon(x) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset \text{ for all } n \in J\}$.

Proposition 4.4. Let $\{E_n\}$ be a sequence of subsets of E . Then

- (a) $\liminf E_n \subseteq \limsup E_n$.
- (b) The sets $\liminf E_n$ and $\limsup E_n$ are closed in E .

Next, we characterize the elements of the upper and lower limit sets of a sequence $\{E_n\}$ by means of sequences of points.

Theorem 4.5. Let $\{E_n\}$ be a sequence of nonempty subsets of E . Then

- (a) $x \in \limsup E_n$ if and only if there exist an increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < \dots$ and points $x_{n_k} \in E_{n_k}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lim x_{n_k} = x$.
- (b) $x \in \liminf E_n$ if and only if there exists a sequence $\{x_n\}$ with $x_n \in E_n$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lim x_n = x$.

Proof. (a) Let $x \in \limsup E_n$. Then there exists an infinite set $J_1 \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $E_n \cap B_1(x) \neq \emptyset$ for every $n \in J_1$. Choose $n_1 \in J_1$ and $x_{n_1} \in E_{n_1} \cap B_1(x)$. Similarly, there exists an infinite set $J_2 \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $E_n \cap B_{\frac{1}{2}}(x) \neq \emptyset$ for every $n \in J_2$. Choose $n_2 \in J_2$ such that $n_1 < n_2$ and $x_{n_2} \in E_{n_2} \cap B_{\frac{1}{2}}(x)$. Proceeding inductively in this way, we construct an increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < \dots$ and a sequence of points $x_{n_k} \in E_{n_k}$ for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $d(x_{n_k}, x) < \frac{1}{k}$. Hence, $\lim x_{n_k} = x$. The converse is immediate.

(b) Let $x \in \liminf E_n$. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, define

$$J_k = \{j \in \mathbb{N} : B_{\frac{1}{k}}(x) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset \text{ for all } n \geq j\}.$$

By hypothesis, each J_k is nonempty. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, define $N_k = \min J_k$. Note that $N_k \leq N_{k+1}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, since $J_{k+1} \subseteq J_k$.

Suppose that there exists $p \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $N_k = N_p$ for all $k \geq p$. Then for every $n \geq N_p$, we have $B_{\frac{1}{k}}(x) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset$ for all $k \geq p$. For each $n < N_p$, choose $x_n \in E_n$, and for each $n \geq N_p$, take $x_n \in B_{\frac{1}{p+n}}(x) \cap E_n$. Then the sequence $\{x_n\}$ satisfies the required conditions, namely $x_n \in E_n$ for all n and $\lim x_n = x$.

Now suppose that for every $p \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists $k > p$ such that $N_k > N_p$. Then we can construct an increasing sequence of natural numbers $1 = n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \dots$ such that $N_{n_1} < N_{n_2} < N_{n_3} < \dots$. Define the sequence $\{x_n\}$ as follows:

- For all $n < N_{n_1}$, choose $x_n \in E_n$.
- For all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and all $N_{n_k} \leq n < N_{n_{k+1}}$, choose $x_n \in E_n \cap B_{\frac{1}{n_k}}(x)$.

Clearly, $x_n \in E_n$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and $\lim x_n = x$. Indeed, let $\epsilon > 0$. Since $\lim \frac{1}{n_k} = 0$, there exists $k^* \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for all $k \geq k^*$, $\frac{1}{n_k} < \epsilon$. If $n \geq N_{n_{k^*}}$, then there exists $k \geq k^*$ such that $N_{n_k} \leq n < N_{n_{k+1}}$. Hence $d(x_n, x) < \frac{1}{n_k} < \epsilon$. \square

Lemma 4.6. *Let $\{E_n\}$ be a sequence of nonempty subsets of E . If $E_* \subseteq E$ is closed and nonempty, and there exists a compact set $K \subseteq E$ such that $E_n \subseteq K$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then*

$$\left[\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq N_\epsilon, E_n \subseteq (E_*)_\epsilon \right] \iff \limsup E_n \subseteq E_*. \quad (4.1)$$

Proof. Assume the left-hand side of (4.1), but suppose that there exists $x \in \limsup E_n$ such that $x \notin E$. There exists $\epsilon > 0$ such that $B_\epsilon(x) \cap (E)_\epsilon = \emptyset$. By hypothesis, there exists $N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $E_n \subseteq (E)_\epsilon$ for all $n \geq N_\epsilon$.

On the other hand, by Theorem 4.5 (a), there exist an increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < \dots$ and points $x_{n_k} \in E_{n_k}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lim x_{n_k} = x$. Let $k^* \in \mathbb{N}$ be such that $N_\epsilon \leq n_{k^*}$ and $d(x_{n_{k^*}}, x) < \epsilon$. Then

$$x_{n_{k^*}} \in B_\epsilon(x) \cap E_{n_{k^*}} \subseteq B_\epsilon(x) \cap (E)_\epsilon,$$

which is a contradiction.

Conversely, assume that $\limsup E_n \subseteq E$, but that the left-hand side of (4.1) does not hold. Then there exist $\epsilon_1 > 0$ and an increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < \dots$ such that $E_{n_k} \not\subseteq (E)_{\epsilon_1}$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Choose $y_{n_k} \in E_{n_k} \setminus (E)_{\epsilon_1}$ for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Since each $y_{n_k} \in E_{n_k} \subseteq K$ and K is compact, there exists a subsequence $\{y_{n_{k_j}}\}$ of $\{y_{n_k}\}$ such that $y_{n_{k_j}} \rightarrow y$ for some $y \in K$. Since each $y_{n_{k_j}} \in X \setminus (E)_{\epsilon_1}$ and this set is closed, it follows that $y \in X \setminus (E)_{\epsilon_1}$. On the other hand, by Theorem 4.5 (a), we have $y \in \limsup E_n$, and by hypothesis $\limsup E_n \subseteq E$. Thus $y \in E \subseteq (E)_{\epsilon_1}$, which is a contradiction. \square

Lemma 4.7. *Let $\{E_n\}$ be a sequence of nonempty subsets of E and let $E_* \subseteq E$ be compact. Then*

$$\left[\forall \epsilon > 0, \exists N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N} : \forall n \geq N_\epsilon, E_* \subseteq (E_n)_\epsilon \right] \iff E_* \subseteq \liminf E_n. \quad (4.2)$$

Proof. Assume the left-hand side of (4.2). Let $x \in E_*$ and $\epsilon > 0$. By hypothesis, there exists $N_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq N_\epsilon$, $d(x, E_n) < \epsilon$. This implies that for each $n \geq N_\epsilon$, there exists $x_n \in E_n$ such that $d(x, x_n) < \epsilon$. Hence $B_\epsilon(x) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset$ for all $n \geq N_\epsilon$, and therefore $x \in \liminf E_n$.

Conversely, assume that $E_* \subseteq \liminf E_n$. Let $\epsilon > 0$. Since E_* is compact, there exist $y_1, \dots, y_m \in E_*$ such that

$$E_* \subseteq \bigcup_{i=1}^m B_{\frac{\epsilon}{2}}(y_i).$$

Since $E_* \subseteq \liminf E_n$, for each $i = 1, \dots, m$, there exists $N_i \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq N_i$, $B_{\frac{\epsilon}{2}}(y_i) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset$. Let $N = \max\{N_1, \dots, N_m\}$ and take $n \geq N$ and $x \in E_*$. Then there exists $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ such that $x \in B_{\frac{\epsilon}{2}}(y_j)$. Since $B_{\frac{\epsilon}{2}}(y_j) \cap E_n \neq \emptyset$, there exists $z \in E_n$ such that $d(z, y_j) < \frac{\epsilon}{2}$. Thus

$$d(x, z) \leq d(x, y_j) + d(y_j, z) < \frac{\epsilon}{2} + \frac{\epsilon}{2} = \epsilon.$$

Therefore, $x \in (E_n)_\epsilon$. □

Theorem 4.8. *Let $\{E_n\}$ be a sequence in \mathcal{S} and let $E_* \in \mathcal{S}$. If there exists a compact set $K \subseteq E$ such that $E_n \subseteq K$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $E_n \rightarrow E_*$ with respect to the Hausdorff metric if and only if*

$$\limsup E_n = \liminf E_n = E_*.$$

Proof. This is an immediate consequence of Lemmas 4.6, 4.7, and Proposition 4.4 (a). □

4.2 Continuity of Set-Valued Mappings in the Hausdorff Metric

Throughout the remainder of this work, we let \mathcal{S} denote the family of all nonempty compact subsets of \mathbb{C} . Recall that the continuity of a function $\tau : (B(X), \|\cdot\|) \rightarrow (\mathcal{S}, d)$ can be characterized in terms of convergent sequences, where d denotes the Hausdorff metric.

Proposition 4.9. *Let d be the Hausdorff metric. Then the mapping $\tau : (B(X), \|\cdot\|) \rightarrow (\mathcal{S}, d)$ is continuous at T if and only if for every sequence (T_n) in $B(X)$ such that $T_n \rightarrow T$, one has $\tau(T_n) \rightarrow \tau(T)$ with respect to the Hausdorff metric.*

Definition 4.10. A function $\tau : (B(X), \|\cdot\|) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ is said to be bounded on convergent sequences if, for every convergent sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $B(X)$, there exists $K \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\tau(T_n) \subseteq K$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

Theorem 4.11. *Let d be the Hausdorff metric and $\tau : (B(X), \|\cdot\|) \rightarrow (\mathcal{S}, d)$ be bounded on convergent sequences. Then, τ is continuous at T if and only if for every sequence (T_n) in $B(X)$ such that $T_n \rightarrow T$,*

$$\limsup \tau(T_n) = \liminf \tau(T_n) = \tau(T). \tag{4.3}$$

Proof. It results by Theorem 4.8. □

From Proposition 4.4, we have that $\liminf \tau(T_n) \subseteq \limsup \tau(T_n)$. Thus, in order to obtain (4.3), it suffices to show that

$$\tau(T) \subseteq \liminf \tau(T_n) \quad \text{and} \quad \limsup \tau(T_n) \subseteq \tau(T).$$

The spectrum, the surjective spectrum, the approximate point spectrum, and several parts of the spectrum can also be regarded as functions from $B(X)$ into \mathcal{S} . The continuity of each of these functions can be characterized as follows.

Proposition 4.12. *If $\tau \in \{\sigma, \sigma_{ap}, \sigma_{su}, \sigma_e, \sigma_w, \sigma_b\}$, then τ is continuous at T if and only if for every sequence $T_n \rightarrow T$,*

$$\tau(T) \subseteq \liminf \tau(T_n) \quad \text{and} \quad \limsup \tau(T_n) \subseteq \tau(T).$$

Proof. According to Theorem 4.11, it suffices to verify that for every convergent sequence $\{T_n\}$ in $B(X)$, there exists a set $K \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\tau(T_n) \subseteq K$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Indeed, suppose that $\{T_n\}$ converges to T . Then there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\|T_n - T\| \leq \varepsilon$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Hence $\|T_n\| \leq \varepsilon + \|T\|$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, and therefore

$$\tau(T_n) \subseteq \sigma(T_n) \subseteq B(0, \|T_n\|) \subseteq B[0, \varepsilon + \|T\|].$$

Thus $B[0, \varepsilon + \|T\|]$ is the required set. □

Definition 4.13. A function $\tau : B(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ is said to be upper (respectively, lower) semi-continuous at T if, whenever $T_n \rightarrow T$, one has

$$\limsup \tau(T_n) \subseteq \tau(T) \quad (\text{respectively, } \tau(T) \subseteq \liminf \tau(T_n)).$$

In general, none of the functions σ , σ_{ap} , σ_{su} , σ_e , σ_w , and σ_b is continuous; see, for instance, Examples 4.38 and 4.44. However, it is known that each of these functions is always upper semicontinuous. For completeness, we include a proof of this fact.

Proposition 4.14. *Let W be a closed subset of $B(X)$ and define a function τ by*

$$\tau(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid \lambda I - T \in W\}, \quad T \in B(X).$$

Then, for every $T \in B(X)$ and every sequence $\{T_n\}$ in $B(X)$ converging to T , one has

$$\limsup \tau(T_n) \subseteq \tau(T).$$

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \limsup \tau(T_n)$ and suppose that $\lambda \notin \tau(T)$. Since E is closed, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $B(\lambda I - T, \varepsilon) \subseteq B(X) \setminus E$. Let $n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \dots$ be a sequence of natural numbers and $\lambda_{n_k} \in \tau(T_{n_k})$ for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lambda_{n_k} \rightarrow \lambda$. Then there exists k_0 such that for all $k \geq k_0$, $\lambda_{n_k} I - T_{n_k} \in B(\lambda I - T, \varepsilon)$. Hence $\lambda_{n_k} I - T_{n_k} \notin E$, which implies that $\lambda_{n_k} \notin \tau(T_{n_k})$, a contradiction. □

The set of invertible operators in $B(X)$ is open in $B(X)$; see [16, Theorem 2.1.3]. Similarly, the set of injective operators with closed range and the set of surjective operators are open in $B(X)$; see [16, Theorem 2.5.6]. Moreover, by Remark 1.13 (d), the sets of Fredholm and Weyl operators are open in $B(X)$, and the set of Browder operators is also open in $B(X)$. From these facts and Propositions 4.14, we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 4.15. *The functions σ , σ_{ap} , σ_{su} , σ_e , σ_w , and σ_b are upper semicontinuous.*

Thus, in order to show that a function $\tau : B(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ is continuous at $T \in B(X)$, where τ is one of the functions σ , σ_{ap} , σ_{su} , σ_e , σ_w , or σ_b , it suffices to prove that for every sequence $\{T_n\}$ in $B(X)$ converging to T , one has

$$\tau(T) \subseteq \liminf \tau(T_n).$$

4.3 Continuity of the Spectrum and Its Parts

We begin this section by identifying subsets of $\sigma(T)$ that are necessarily contained in $\liminf \tau(T_n)$, where $\tau \in \{\sigma, \sigma_{ap}, \sigma_{su}\}$, independently of the operator T . Our first objective is to establish that the isolated points of $\sigma(T)$ are contained in $\liminf \sigma(T_n)$ whenever $T_n \rightarrow T$. The argument we present is due to Newburgh [37].

Proposition 4.16. *If $T_n, T \in B(X)$ are such that $T_n \rightarrow T$, then*

$$\text{iso } \sigma(T) \subseteq \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

where $\text{iso } \sigma(T)$ denotes the set of isolated points of $\sigma(T)$.

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$ and suppose that $\lambda \notin \liminf \sigma(T_n)$. Then there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ and a sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \dots$ such that $\sigma(T_{n_k}) \cap B(\lambda, \varepsilon) = \emptyset$ for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Since $T_{n_k} \rightarrow T$ and $\{\lambda\}$ is a spectral set for T , by Theorem 1.12, there exists $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for each $k \geq k_0$,

$$\Lambda_k = \sigma(T_{n_k}) \cap B\left(\lambda, \frac{\varepsilon}{2}\right)$$

is a spectral set for T_{n_k} and

$$\lim_{k_0 \leq k \rightarrow \infty} P(T_{n_k}, \Lambda_k) = P(T, \lambda).$$

Each Λ_k is empty, hence each spectral projection $P(T_{n_k}, \Lambda_k)$ is the zero operator (see Observation 1.8 (d)). This implies that $P(T, \lambda) = 0$, which is a contradiction (see again Observation 1.8 (d)). \square

When λ is an isolated point of the spectrum of T and the range of the spectral projection $P(T, \lambda)$ is finite-dimensional, we obtain a stronger condition, as shown in the following proposition:

Proposition 4.17. *If $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence in $B(X)$ converging to $T \in B(X)$, then*

$$\pi_0(T) \subseteq \liminf \pi_0(T_n).$$

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$. Then there exists $\zeta > 0$ such that $[B[\lambda, \zeta] \setminus \{\lambda\}] \cap \sigma(T) = \emptyset$. By Theorem 1.12 and since $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$, for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ there exists $N_k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, for every $n \geq N_k$,

$$\Lambda_{n,k} := \sigma(T_n) \cap B\left(\lambda, \frac{\zeta}{k}\right)$$

is a nonempty spectral set for T_n and

$$\dim R(P_{n,k}) = \dim R(P),$$

where $P_{n,k} := P(T_n, \Lambda_{n,k})$ and $P := P(T, \lambda)$. Without loss of generality, assume that $N_1 < N_2 < N_3 < \dots$. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and each $n \in [N_k, N_{k+1})$, choose $\lambda_n \in \Lambda_{n,k}$. Since $\dim R(P) < \infty$, by Theorem 1.10, for every $n \geq N_1$, λ_n is an isolated point of $\sigma(T_n)$ and the range of $P(T_n, \lambda_n)$ is finite-dimensional. Thus, for every $n \geq N_1$, $\lambda_n \in \pi_0(T_n)$. Finally, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \lambda_n = \lambda$. Indeed, let $\varepsilon > 0$ be arbitrary. There exists $A \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, for every $k \geq A$, $\frac{\zeta}{k} < \varepsilon$. If $n \geq N_A$, then there exists $k \geq A$ such that $n \in [N_k, N_{k+1})$, and hence $|\lambda_n - \lambda| < \frac{\zeta}{k} < \varepsilon$. \square

Another collection of points that is included in $\liminf \sigma(T_n)$ is given by the following proposition:

Proposition 4.18. *If $T_n, T \in B(X)$ are such that $T_n \rightarrow T$, then*

$$\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_{ap}(T) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

Proof. Indeed, let $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_{ap}(T)$. Then $\lambda I - T$ is an injective operator with closed range. This implies that $\lambda I - T$ is a semi-Fredholm operator and $i(\lambda I - T) \leq 0$. Since $\lambda I - T$ is not invertible, we have $i(\lambda I - T) < 0$. Now, if there exists an increasing sequence of natural numbers $\{n_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $\lambda I - T_{n_k}$ is invertible for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, then since $i(\lambda I - T_{n_k}) = 0$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, it follows from the continuity of the index that $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, there exists $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, for every $n \geq N$, $\lambda \in \sigma(T_n)$. Hence, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$. \square

From the previous proposition we immediately obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 4.19. *If σ_{ap} is continuous at $T \in B(X)$, then σ is continuous at T .*

Recall that $\rho_{sF}^+(T)$ and $\rho_{sF}^-(T)$ are, respectively, the sets of all $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ for which $\lambda I - T \in \Phi^\pm(X)$ and, respectively,

$$i(\lambda I - T) > 0, \quad i(\lambda I - T) < 0.$$

Proposition 4.20. *Let $T \in B(X)$. Then*

$$\rho_{sF}^+(T) \subset \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n)$$

and

$$\rho_{sF}^-(T) \subset \liminf \sigma_{su}(T_n)$$

for every sequence $T_n \rightarrow T$.

Proof. The proof is analogous to that of Proposition 4.18. □

Definition 4.21. An element T of $B(X)$ is called a shift operator if

$$\alpha(T) = 0, \quad \beta(T) = 1, \quad \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} R(T^n) = \{0\}.$$

As a consequence of Proposition 4.20, the class of shift operators that are isometries are points of continuity of the spectrum. Shift operators are operators whose spectrum and some of its parts are already known. However, the continuity of the spectrum in this class of operators provides us with a potential source of examples and counterexamples that are useful in the present work. The next proposition provides a generalization of [42].

Proposition 4.22. *If $T \in B(X)$ is a shift operator and an isometry, then*

(a) σ and σ_{su} are continuous functions at T ,

(b) σ and σ_{ap} are continuous functions at T^* .

Proof. Clearly T is a Fredholm operator and $i(T) = -1$. Now, C. Schmoeger shows in [43] that if $A \in B(X)$ is a shift operator and an isometry, then $\sigma(A) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| \leq 1\}$ and, for each $\lambda \in \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| < 1\}$, $\lambda I - A$ is a shift operator. In this way, we have

$$\sigma(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| \leq 1\} \subset \overline{\rho_{sF}^-(T)}.$$

On the other hand, Proposition 4.20 and Proposition 4.4 imply that

$$\overline{\rho_{sF}^-(T)} \subset \liminf \sigma_{su}(T_n).$$

Since $\sigma_{su}(T) \subset \sigma(T)$, we conclude that $\sigma_{su}(T) \subset \liminf \sigma_{su}(T_n)$, that is, σ_{su} is continuous at T . By duality, σ_{ap} is continuous at T^* . □

Proposition 4.23. *Let $T \in B(X)$. For every sequence $T_n \rightarrow T$, we have*

$$\{\lambda \in \sigma(T) \cap \rho_{sF}(T) \mid p(\lambda I - T) < \infty\} \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

and

$$\{\lambda \in \sigma(T) \cap \rho_{sF}(T) \mid q(\lambda I - T) < \infty\} \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

Proof. We will prove only the first inclusion. Let $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$ such that $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_{\pm}(X)$ and $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. By Theorem 1.20 (a), $i(\lambda I - T) \leq 0$. If $i(\lambda I - T) < 0$, then $\lambda \in \rho_{sF}^{-}(T)$, and by Proposition 4.20, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{su}(T_n)$. Since $\liminf \sigma_{su}(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n)$, we obtain $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$.

On the other hand, if $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$, then $\alpha(\lambda I - T) = \beta(\lambda I - T)$, and as a consequence of Theorem 1.20 (d), $q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Then, by Theorem 1.22, $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma(T)$. From Proposition 4.16, it follows that $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$. \square

As an immediate consequence of the previous proposition, we state the following theorem.

Theorem 4.24. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be such that $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for every $\lambda \notin \sigma_e(T)$. If σ_e is continuous at T , then σ is continuous at T .*

Proof. Let $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$. Suppose that $\lambda \notin \liminf \sigma(T_n)$. Then there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ does not intersect infinitely many $\sigma(T_n)$. Thus, we can choose a subsequence $\{T_{n_k}\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that

$$d(\lambda, \sigma(T_{n_k})) > \varepsilon \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Since clearly

$$d(\lambda, \sigma(T_{n_k})) \leq d(\lambda, \sigma_e(T_{n_k})),$$

and since σ_e is continuous at T , we obtain that $\lambda \notin \sigma_e(T)$. Hence $\lambda I - T \in \Phi(X)$ and, by hypothesis, $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Therefore, by Proposition 4.23, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$, which is a contradiction. \square

Conway and Morrel in [13, 14] have characterized the continuity of the spectrum and the approximate point spectrum in the algebra $B(H)$, where H is a Hilbert space. They prove that σ is continuous at $T \in B(H)$ if and only if, for each $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \overline{\rho_{sF}^{\pm}(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T) \cup \pi_0(T)$.

They also show that σ_{ap} is continuous at $T \in B(H)$ if and only if σ is continuous at T , $\rho_{sF}^{-}(T) \cap \sigma_p(T) = \emptyset$, $\rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T) = \text{int } \overline{\rho_{sF}^{-\infty}(T)}$, and for each $-\infty < k \leq -1$, it holds that for every $\lambda \in \text{int } \overline{\rho_{sF}^k(T)} \setminus \rho_{sF}^k(T)$ (where $\rho_{sF}^k(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid i(\lambda I - T) = k\}$) and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$.

We also cite L. Burlando, who in [11] provided some sufficient conditions for the continuity of σ in the algebra $B(X)$, where X is a Banach space.

Now, following the idea of Conway and Morrel, we will prove that the approximate point spectrum is continuous at $T \in B(X)$, where X is a Banach space, when T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$ and, for each $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi^+(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$.

Lemma 4.25 ([13]). *Let $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset B(X)$ be such that $T_n \rightarrow T$.*

- (a) *If C is a connected component of $\sigma(T)$ and U is an open set containing C , then there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, U contains a connected component of $\sigma(T_n)$.*
- (b) *If C is a connected component of $\sigma_e(T)$ and U is an open set containing C , then there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, U contains a connected component of $\sigma_e(T_n)$.*

Proof. The proof works for any Banach algebra, so we only prove part (a).

Let C be a connected component of $\sigma(T)$ and U an open subset of \mathbb{C} containing C . The set $\sigma(T) \setminus U$ is closed in $\sigma(T)$, and $C \cap [\sigma(T) \setminus U] = \emptyset$. Hence, there exists a nonempty set X_1 that is both open and closed in $\sigma(T)$ such that

$$C \subset X_1 \subset U.$$

Observe that $U \cap [\mathbb{C} \setminus (\sigma(T) \setminus X_1)]$ is open and contains X_1 . By Theorem 1.6, there exists a Cauchy domain D such that

$$X_1 \subset D \subset \bar{D} \subset U \cap [\mathbb{C} \setminus (\sigma(T) \setminus X_1)].$$

Let Γ be the Cauchy contour determined by the boundary of D . Then Γ separates X_1 from $\sigma(T) \setminus X_1$. By Theorem 1.12, there exists $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq N$, $\Gamma \subset \rho(T_n)$, $\Lambda_n = \sigma(T_n) \cap D$ is a spectral set for T_n , and Γ separates Λ_n from $\sigma(T_n) \setminus \Lambda_n$. Moreover, if

$$P(T_n, \Lambda_n) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma} (z - T_n)^{-1} dz, \quad P(T, X_1) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma} (z - T)^{-1} dz,$$

then $P(T_n, \Lambda_n) \rightarrow P(T, X_1)$. Since $P(T, X_1) \neq 0$ (because $X_1 \neq \emptyset$), there exists $n_0 \geq N$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, $P(T_n, \Lambda_n) \neq 0$. Hence, for every $n \geq n_0$, $\Lambda_n \neq \emptyset$.

Fix $n \geq n_0$. Since Λ_n is both closed and open in $\sigma(T_n)$ and $\Lambda_n \neq \emptyset$, there exists a connected component C_n of $\sigma(T_n)$ such that $C_n \subset \Lambda_n$. Note that $\Lambda_n \subset D \subset U$, hence $C_n \subset U$. Thus, U contains a connected component of $\sigma(T_n)$ for all $n \geq n_0$. \square

The following lemma is a generalization of [14, Lemma 3.1] to the case of Banach spaces.

Lemma 4.26. *Let $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset B(X)$ be such that $T_n \rightarrow T$. If $\lambda \notin \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)}$ is such that for every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, then*

$$\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{sF}(T_n).$$

Proof. Let $\varepsilon > 0$. Since $\lambda \notin \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)}$, there exists $r > 0$ such that $B(\lambda, r) \cap \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} = \emptyset$. Set $\varepsilon_1 = \min\{\varepsilon, r\}$. By hypothesis, $B(\lambda, \varepsilon_1)$ contains a connected component C of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$. Since $C \cap \overline{\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)} = \emptyset$, it follows from Lemma 3.4 that C is a connected component of $\sigma_e(T)$.

By Lemma 4.25 (b), there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon_1)$ contains a connected component C_n of $\sigma_e(T_n)$. Now, by Lemma 3.3 (c), for every $n \geq n_0$,

$$\emptyset \neq \partial C_n \subset \partial \sigma_e(T_n) \subset \sigma_{sF}(T_n).$$

Thus, for every $n \geq n_0$, $B(\lambda, \varepsilon) \cap \sigma_{sF}(T_n) \neq \emptyset$. \square

Restricting the set $\phi_{\pm\infty}(T)$ to $\phi_{+\infty}(T)$, the previous lemma can be stated as follows:

Lemma 4.27. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be such that $i(\beta I - T) \geq 0$ for every $\beta \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. If $T_n \rightarrow T$ in $B(X)$ and $\lambda \notin \overline{\phi_{+\infty}(T)}$ is such that for every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected*

component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, then

$$\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{sF}(T_n).$$

Proof. The proof follows in the same way as that of Lemma 4.26, using Lemma 3.5. \square

Theorem 4.28. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be such that $q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ for every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. If for each $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_+(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, then σ_{ap} is continuous at T .*

Proof. Let $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence in $B(X)$ such that $T_n \rightarrow T$. Since $\phi_+(T) \subset \rho_{sF}^+(T)$ and the latter, by Proposition 4.20, is contained in $\liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n)$, we obtain that

$$\overline{\phi_+(T)} \subset \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n).$$

Now let $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_+(T)}$. If $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$, then by hypothesis $q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$, which implies, by Theorem 1.20 (b), that $\beta(\lambda I - T) \leq \alpha(\lambda I - T)$. Clearly, $\lambda I - T$ is semi-Fredholm, hence $i(\lambda I - T) \geq 0$. Note that $i(\lambda I - T)$ cannot be positive, thus $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$, and therefore $\alpha(\lambda I - T) = \beta(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Then, by Theorem 1.20 (d), $p(\lambda I - T) = q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Consequently, by Theorem 1.22, $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$. But by Proposition 4.17,

$$\pi_0(T) \subset \liminf \pi_0(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n),$$

and hence $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n)$.

If $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T)$, then $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_+(T)}$, and by hypothesis, for every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$. Then, by Lemma 4.27, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{sF}(T_n)$. Since $\sigma_{sF}(T_n) \subset \sigma_{ap}(T_n)$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, it follows that $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n)$. \square

Consider $T \in B(X)$ and let $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. Then $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_{\pm}(X)$, which implies (see Theorem 1.29) that $\lambda I - T$ is essentially semi-regular, and therefore it is of Kato type. Now observe, by Theorem 1.31,

$$T^* \text{ has SVEP at } \lambda \iff q(\lambda I - T) < \infty.$$

Thus, the previous theorem can be equivalently stated as follows:

Theorem 4.29. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be such that T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. If for each $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_+(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, then σ_{ap} is continuous at T .*

In the previous result, the set of λ for which the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, for every $\varepsilon > 0$, can be reduced as shown in the following corollary.

Corollary 4.30. *Let $T \in B(X)$ be such that T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T)$. If for each $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_+(T)} \cup \pi_0(T)$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, then σ_{ap} is continuous at T .*

Proof. The proof is analogous to that of Theorem 4.28. It suffices to observe that

$$\overline{\pi_0(T)} \subset \liminf \pi_0(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n),$$

where the first inclusion follows from Proposition 4.17. \square

4.4 Continuity of the Spectrum and Browder-Type Theorems

S. V. Djordjević and Y. M. Han in [19] proved that if the Browder spectrum function is continuous at an operator $T \in B(H)$, where H is a Hilbert space, then T satisfies Browder's theorem. Moreover, under the hypothesis that T satisfies Browder's theorem, they show that the conditions σ_b is continuous, σ_w is continuous, and σ is continuous are equivalent. However, there is an omission in this last statement, as we will see later. In this section, we also present some relations of this type.

Proposition 4.31. *Let X be a Banach space. If $T \in B(X)$, then*

$$\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) = \pi_0(T) \cup \text{int} \left(\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) \right).$$

Proof. Clearly,

$$\text{int} \left(\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) \right) \subset \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T).$$

If $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$, then by Theorem 1.22, $p(\lambda I - T) = q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ and $\alpha(\lambda I - T) < \infty$, which by Theorem 1.20 (c) implies

$$p(\lambda I - T) = q(\lambda I - T) < \infty, \quad \alpha(\lambda I - T) = \beta(\lambda I - T) < \infty,$$

hence $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$. Therefore,

$$\pi_0(T) \cup \text{int} \left(\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) \right) \subset \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T).$$

For the reverse inclusion, let $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$. If $\lambda \notin \text{int} \sigma(T)$, then $\lambda \in \partial \sigma(T)$ and by Remark 1.24 (c), both T and T^* have SVEP at λ . Since $\lambda I - T \in \Phi(X)$, it follows from Theorems 1.30 and 1.31 that $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$ and $q(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Hence, by Theorem 1.22, $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$.

If $\lambda \in \text{int} \sigma(T)$, then $\lambda \in \text{int} \left(\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) \right)$, since $\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \sigma_w(T)$ and this set is open. \square

Let H be a Hilbert space and let $A \in B(H)$ be a point of continuity of σ . Then, by [13, Theorem 3.1], for each $\lambda \in \sigma(A) \setminus \overline{\rho_{sF}^\pm(A)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lrc}(A) \cup \pi_0(A)$.

Thus, since $\sigma(A) \setminus \sigma_w(A) \subset \sigma(A) \setminus \overline{\rho_{sF}^\pm(A)}$ and

$$\text{int} \left(\sigma(A) \setminus \sigma_w(A) \right) \cap \left(\pi_0(A) \cup \sigma_{lrc}(A) \right) = \emptyset,$$

it follows that

$$\text{int} \left(\sigma(A) \setminus \sigma_w(A) \right) = \emptyset.$$

From this and Proposition 4.31, we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 4.32. *Let H be a Hilbert space. If σ is continuous at $T \in B(H)$, then T satisfies Browder's theorem.*

Proof. By Proposition 4.18,

$$\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) = \pi_0(T) \cup \text{int} \left(\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) \right),$$

and from the previous argument, $\text{int} \left(\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) \right) = \emptyset$. Thus, $\sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) = \pi_0(T)$, that is, T satisfies Browder's theorem. \square

The converse of the previous theorem does not hold; see Example 4.38 below.

Theorem 4.33. *Let X be a Banach space. If $T \in B(X)$ is a point of continuity of σ_b , then T is a point of continuity of σ .*

Proof. Let $T_n \rightarrow T$ and $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$. If $\lambda \in \sigma_b(T)$, then

$$\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_b(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

If $\lambda \notin \sigma_b(T)$, then $\lambda I - T \in B_+(X) \cap B_-(X)$, hence $\lambda I - T \in \Phi(X)$ and

$$p(\lambda I - T) < \infty, \quad q(\lambda I - T) < \infty.$$

Thus, by Theorem 1.22, $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$, and by Proposition 4.17,

$$\lambda \in \liminf \pi_0(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

\square

Moreover, when $T \in B(X)$ satisfies Browder's theorem, the continuity of σ_w at T implies the continuity of σ_b at T . The converse also holds when T is defined on a Hilbert space H .

Theorem 4.34. *Let H be a Hilbert space. If $T \in B(H)$ satisfies Browder's theorem, then σ_w is continuous at T if and only if σ_b is continuous at T .*

Proof. This theorem is stated in [31, Theorem 14.17], which asserts that σ_b is continuous at T if and only if σ_w is continuous at T and $\sigma_w(T) = \sigma_b(T)$. \square

Corollary 4.35. [19, Theorem 2.1] *Let H be a Hilbert space. If σ_b is continuous at $T \in B(H)$, then T satisfies Browder's theorem.*

On the other hand, even when Browder's theorem holds for an operator $T \in B(H)$, the following statements are true:

$$\sigma \text{ is continuous at } T \not\Rightarrow \sigma_w \text{ is continuous at } T,$$

σ is continuous at $T \not\Rightarrow \sigma_b$ is continuous at T .

To see this, refer to Example 4.44 and Remark 4.45. Similarly to Theorem 4.32, we obtain a relationship between the continuity of the approximate point spectrum and the a -Browder theorem.

Theorem 4.36. *Let H be a Hilbert space. If σ_{ap} is continuous at $T \in B(H)$, then T satisfies the a -Browder theorem.*

Proof. Recall that if σ_{ap} is continuous at T , then $\sigma_p(T) \cap \rho_{sF}^-(T) = \emptyset$. According to Theorem 2.6 (b),(c), it suffices to prove that

$$\sigma_{ap}(T) = \sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \text{iso } \sigma_{ap}(T).$$

It is clear that $\sigma_{wa}(T) \cup \text{iso } \sigma_{ap}(T) \subset \sigma_{ap}(T)$. Let $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(T)$ and suppose that $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$. Then, by Theorem 2.3 (b), $\lambda I - T \in \Phi^+(H)$ and $i(\lambda I - T) \leq 0$. If $i(\lambda I - T) < 0$, then $\lambda \in \rho_{sF}^-(T)$ and therefore $\lambda \notin \sigma_p(T)$. Hence $N(\lambda I - T) = \{0\}$. Since $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(T)$, it follows that $R(\lambda I - T)$ is not closed. This contradicts the fact that $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_+(H)$. Therefore, $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$, which implies that $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$.

On the other hand, the continuity of σ_{ap} at T and Theorem 4.19 imply that T is a point of continuity of σ . Hence, by Theorem 4.32, T satisfies Browder's theorem. Thus,

$$\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T) = \pi_0(T),$$

which implies that $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma_{ap}(T)$. □

4.5 Continuity of the Spectrum and Compact Perturbations

Recall that an operator $K \in B(X)$ is compact (that is, $K \in K(X)$) if for every bounded sequence $\{x_n\}$ in X , the sequence $\{Kx_n\}$ contains a convergent subsequence. It is known that the nonzero points of the spectrum of a compact operator K are isolated points of $\sigma(K)$. This implies, by Proposition 4.16, that

$$\sigma(K) = \overline{\text{iso } \sigma(K)} \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

for any sequence $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset B(X)$ converging to K . In this way, the spectrum is continuous at every compact operator K .

Let $T \in B(X)$. In practice, it is useful to know whether the spectrum function is continuous under perturbations of T by a compact operator K , that is, at $T + K$. Observe that even though σ is continuous on $K(X)$, it is not necessarily true that the restriction of σ to $K(X) + \{T\}$ is continuous (see Example 4.38).

In this section, we first present conditions under which

$$\sigma|_{K(X) + \{T\}} : K(X) + \{T\} \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$$

is continuous. Afterwards, we study the continuity of

$$\sigma : B(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$$

at perturbations of the form $T + K$, when T is a point of continuity of σ .

Definition 4.37. Two operators $T, S \in B(X)$ are said to be similar if there exists an invertible operator $U \in B(X)$ such that $UT = SU$.

If $T, S \in B(X)$ are similar operators, then

$$\sigma(T) = \sigma(S).$$

Example 4.38. Let $U : \ell^2(\mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \ell^2(\mathbb{N})$ be the unilateral shift defined by

$$U(x) = (0, x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots), \quad x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots),$$

and let T, K_n be operators on $\ell^2(\mathbb{N}) \oplus \ell^2(\mathbb{N})$ defined by

$$T = \begin{pmatrix} U & 0 \\ 0 & U^* \end{pmatrix}, \quad K_n = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{n}(I - UU^*) \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\dim R(K_n) = 1$. This implies that $\{K_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a sequence of compact operators. Note that $T + K_n \rightarrow T$. However,

$$\sigma(T + K_n) \not\rightarrow \sigma(T),$$

since

$$\sigma(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| \leq 1\}, \quad \sigma(T + K_n) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}.$$

The latter follows from the fact that each $T + K_n$ is similar to $T + K_1$, and $T + K_1$ is a unitary operator.

Recall that

$$\sigma_b(T) = \bigcap_{\substack{K \in K(X) \\ TK=KT}} \sigma(T + K) \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma_w(T) = \bigcap_{K \in K(X)} \sigma(T + K). \quad (4.4)$$

Theorem 4.39. Let $T \in B(X)$ and let $K_n, K \in K(X)$ be such that $K_n \rightarrow K$ and $TK = KT$. If $\lambda I - T$ has finite ascent for every $\lambda \in \sigma_p(T)$, then

$$\sigma(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma(T + K).$$

Proof. It is known that the spectrum function σ is upper semicontinuous, hence

$$\limsup \sigma(T + K_n) \subset \sigma(T + K).$$

Therefore, it suffices to verify that

$$\sigma(T + K) \subset \liminf \sigma(T + K_n).$$

Let $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K)$. If $\lambda \in \sigma_w(T)$, then by (4.4), $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K_n)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Thus, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T + K_n)$.

Assume that $\lambda \notin \sigma_w(T)$. This implies that $\lambda I - T \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$. Consequently, $\lambda I - (T + K) \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - (T + K)) = 0$ (see Remark 1.14 (b)). If $\lambda \notin \sigma(T)$, then $\lambda I - T$ is invertible and therefore $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Now, if $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$, then $\alpha(\lambda I - T) > 0$, hence $\lambda \in \sigma_p(T)$, and by hypothesis $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Thus, in any case, $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Observe that

$$(\lambda I - T)(-K) = -\lambda K + TK = -\lambda K + KT = (-K)(\lambda I - T).$$

Then, by Theorem 1.23, we obtain that $p((\lambda I - T) - K) < \infty$. Since $p(\lambda I - (T + K)) < \infty$ and $i(\lambda I - (T + K)) = 0$, it follows from Theorem 1.20 (d) that $q(\lambda I - (T + K)) < \infty$, which implies that $\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K)$ (see Theorem 1.22). Consequently, by Proposition 4.17,

$$\lambda \in \liminf \pi_0(T + K_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T + K_n).$$

□

Next, we establish other sufficient conditions for the convergence $\sigma(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma(T + K)$ involving the concept of SVEP.

Corollary 4.40. *If $T \in B(X)$ has SVEP at every $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$, then for each $K \in K(X)$ such that*

$$(i) \quad TK = KT, \text{ or}$$

$$(ii) \quad \text{int } \sigma(T + K) \subset \sigma(T),$$

it follows that $\sigma(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma(T + K)$ for any sequence $\{K_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset K(X)$ converging to K .

Proof. Following the idea of the proof of Theorem 4.39, it suffices to consider the case $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$. By hypothesis and Theorem 2.5, T satisfies Browder's theorem and, consequently, for $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$, $\lambda I - T$ is a Fredholm operator of index zero with finite ascent and descent.

Assume condition (i). Since K commutes with T , $\lambda I - (T + K)$ is a Fredholm operator of index zero with finite ascent and descent, hence

$$\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K) \subset \liminf \sigma(T + K_n).$$

Assume condition (ii). If $\lambda \notin \sigma(T)$, then clearly $\lambda \notin \text{int } \sigma(T + K)$. If $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$, then $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$, hence $\lambda \notin \text{int } \sigma(T)$. Since $\text{int } \sigma(T + K) \subset \text{int } \sigma(T)$, it follows that $\lambda \notin \text{int } \sigma(T + K)$. Thus, in any case, $\lambda \notin \text{int } \sigma(T + K)$, and therefore $\lambda \in \partial \sigma(T + K)$. By Remark 1.24 (c), $T + K$ has SVEP at λ , and by Remark 1.14 (b), $\lambda I - (T + K) \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - (T + K)) = 0$. Note

that $\lambda I - (T + K)$ is a Kato-type operator (see Theorem 1.29). Consequently, by Theorem 1.30, $p(\lambda I - (T + K)) < \infty$, and using Theorem 1.20 (d), we also obtain $q(\lambda I - (T + K)) < \infty$. Thus,

$$\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K) \subset \liminf \sigma(T + K_n).$$

□

Corollary 4.41. *Let H be a Hilbert space and let $T \in B(H)$ be a point of continuity of the spectrum. If K is a compact operator that commutes with T , then*

$$\sigma(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma(T + K)$$

for any sequence $\{K_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset K(H)$ converging to K .

Proof. Observe that, by Theorem 4.32, T satisfies Browder's theorem. With this, the proof follows in a manner similar to that of Corollary 4.40. □

A necessary and sufficient condition for T to satisfy the a -Browder theorem is that either T or T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{aw}(T)$ (see Theorem 2.7).

Theorem 4.42. *Let $T \in B(X)$ and $K \in K(X)$ be such that $TK = KT$. If $\{K_n\}$ is a sequence in $K(X)$ such that $K_n \rightarrow K$, then*

(a) $\sigma_{ap}(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma_{ap}(T + K)$, when T^* has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{aw}(T)$, and

(b) $\sigma_{su}(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma_{su}(T + K)$, when T has SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{ws}(T)$.

Proof. We prove only part (a); part (b) follows by duality.

(a) Let $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(T + K)$. If $\lambda \in \sigma_{wa}(T)$, then $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(T + F)$ for every $F \in K(X)$, and consequently $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T + K_n)$.

Suppose that $\lambda \notin \sigma_{wa}(T)$. By hypothesis, T satisfies the a -Browder theorem, hence $\lambda \notin \sigma_{ub}(T)$ and therefore $\lambda I - T \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $p(\lambda I - T) < \infty$. Note that, by Theorem 1.20 (a), $i(\lambda I - T) \leq 0$. Also, since T^* has SVEP at λ , we have $i(\lambda I - T) \geq 0$ (see (1.6)). Thus, $i(\lambda I - T) = 0$. Since $TK = KT$, it follows from Remark 1.14 (b) and Theorem 1.23 that

$$i(\lambda I - (T + K)) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad p(\lambda I - (T + K)) < \infty.$$

Then, by Theorem 1.20 (d), $q(\lambda I - (T + K)) < \infty$. Therefore, $\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K)$. By Proposition 4.17,

$$\lambda \in \liminf \pi_0(T + K_n) \subset \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T + K_n).$$

□

Next, we study the continuity of $\sigma : B(X) \rightarrow \mathcal{S}$ at the operator $T + K$, for $T \in B(X)$ and $K \in K(X)$.

Observe that in Corollary 4.41, the hypothesis that T is a point of continuity of σ was sufficient to guarantee that $\sigma(T + K_n) \rightarrow \sigma(T + K)$ for any compact operator K commuting

with T and any sequence $K_n \rightarrow K$. From this situation, the following question arises: assuming that T is a point of continuity of σ , is $T + K$ also a point of continuity of σ for any compact operator K that commutes with T ?

In the general setting, the answer to this question is negative, as we show in the following example. Before that, let us state a known result:

Proposition 4.43 ([5], Theorem 3.1). *If Σ is a nonempty subset of \mathbb{C} and $A \in B(H)$, then there exists a sequence of operators $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $B(H)$ such that $\sigma(A_n) \subset \Sigma$ for all n , and $\|A - A_n\| \rightarrow 0$, if and only if:*

(a) $\phi_{\pm}(A) \subset \Sigma$;

(b) each connected component of $\pi_0(A) \cup \sigma_{lre}(A)$ intersects $\bar{\Sigma}$.

Example 4.44. Let $\alpha_{nk} = \left(1 + \frac{1}{n}\right) \exp\left(\frac{2\pi ik}{n}\right)$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $1 \leq k \leq n$, and let $M : \ell^2(\mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \ell^2(\mathbb{N})$ be the diagonal operator defined by

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_{11} & & & \\ & \alpha_{21} & & \\ & & \alpha_{22} & \\ & & & \ddots \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then $\sigma_p(M) = \{\alpha_{nk} \mid n \in \mathbb{N}, 1 \leq k \leq n\}$ and each eigenvalue of M has finite geometric multiplicity.

Let $\{\alpha_m\}_{m \in \mathbb{N}}$ be an enumeration of $\{\alpha_{11}, \alpha_{21}, \alpha_{22}, \alpha_{31}, \dots\}$. It is not difficult to prove that

$$\lambda \in \rho(M) = \mathbb{C} \setminus \sigma(M) \iff \inf_m |\lambda - \alpha_m| > 0.$$

Thus,

$$\sigma(M) = \{\alpha_m\}_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}.$$

For each $m \in \mathbb{N}$, since $\inf\{|\alpha_m - \alpha_j| : j \in \mathbb{N}, j \neq m\} > 0$ and for each $\{y_j\} \in \overline{R(\alpha_m I - M)}$ we have $y_m = 0$, it follows that $R(\alpha_m I - M)$ is closed in $\ell^2(\mathbb{N})$. Hence $\alpha_m I - M$ is semi-Fredholm and α_m is an isolated point of $\sigma(M)$. Consequently $\{\alpha_m\} \subset \pi_0(M)$.

Note that $\sigma_{lre}(M) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}$. Thus $\rho_{sF}^{\pm}(M) = \emptyset$, $\pi_0(M) = \{\alpha_m\}$, and $\sigma_w(M) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\}$.

Since $\sigma(M) = \overline{\pi_0(M)}$, by Proposition 4.17,

$$\sigma(M) = \overline{\pi_0(M)} \subset \liminf \pi_0(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n)$$

for any sequence $T_n \rightarrow M$. Therefore σ is continuous at M .

Now M is a normal operator, hence by [38, Theorem 4.1], there exists a compact operator K commuting with M such that $\sigma(M + K) = \sigma_w(M)$. Thus $\pi_0(M + K) = \emptyset$ and $\rho_{sF}^{\pm}(M + K) = \rho_{sF}^{\pm}(M) = \emptyset$.

Fix $\lambda_0 \in \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : |\lambda| = 1\}$ and $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : |\lambda| = 1\} \not\subset B(\lambda_0, \varepsilon)$. Let $D = \mathbb{C} \setminus B(\lambda_0, \varepsilon)$. Then:

- (i) $\rho_{sF}^\pm(M + K) \subset D$;
- (ii) every connected component of $\pi_0(M + K) \cup \sigma_{lre}(M + K) = \sigma_{lre}(M)$ intersects D .

By Proposition 4.43, there exists a sequence $\{A_n\}$ such that $A_n \rightarrow M + K$ and $\sigma(A_n) \subset D$. Hence $\sigma(A_n) \not\rightarrow \sigma(M + K)$.

Conclusion: σ is continuous at M , but there exists a compact operator K commuting with M such that σ is not continuous at $M + K$.

Remark 4.45. The operator M defined in Example 4.44 is not a point of continuity of σ_w . Indeed, let $\{A_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$, K , and D be as in Example 4.44. Then $A_n - K \rightarrow M$ and, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\sigma(A_n) \subset D$. Observe that, for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\sigma_w(A_n - K) = \sigma_w(A_n) \subset \sigma(A_n) \subset D.$$

Therefore, since

$$\sigma_w(M) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} \mid |\lambda| = 1\},$$

it follows that

$$\sigma_w(A_n - K) \not\rightarrow \sigma_w(M),$$

that is, σ_w is not continuous at M .

Theorem 4.46. *Let X be a Banach space. If $T \in B(X)$ is such that for each $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_\pm(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$, then σ is continuous at $T + K$ for every $K \in K(X)$ such that $T + K$ satisfies Browder's theorem.*

Proof. Let $\{T_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \subset B(X)$ be such that $T_n \rightarrow T + K$ and let $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K)$.

If $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_\pm(T)}$, then by hypothesis and Lemma 4.26,

$$\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{lre}(T_n - K).$$

Since for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have $\sigma_{lre}(T_n - K) = \sigma_{lre}(T_n)$, it follows that

$$\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{lre}(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

If $\lambda \in \overline{\phi_\pm(T)}$, then either

$$\lambda \in \overline{\phi_+(T)} = \overline{\phi_+(T + K)} \subset \liminf \sigma_{ap}(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

(see Proposition 4.20), or

$$\lambda \in \overline{\phi_-(T)} = \overline{\phi_-(T + K)} \subset \liminf \sigma_{su}(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

Now suppose that $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T) \cup \Phi^\pm(T)$. Then $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(T + K) \cup \Phi^\pm(T + K)$, which implies that $\lambda I - (T + K) \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(\lambda I - (T + K)) = 0$. Thus $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K) \setminus \sigma_w(T + K)$. Since $T + K$ satisfies Browder's theorem, it follows that $\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K)$. Hence, by Proposition 4.17,

$$\lambda \in \liminf \pi_0(T_n) \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n).$$

□

Now let H be a Hilbert space, and let $A \in B(H)$ be a point of continuity of σ . Then, by [13, Theorem 3.1], for each $\lambda \in \sigma(A) \setminus \overline{\rho_{sF}^\pm(A)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(A) \cup \pi_0(A)$. This implies that for any $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(A) \setminus \overline{\phi_\pm(A)} \cup \pi_0(A)$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(A)$. This observation will be used in the proof of the following corollary.

Corollary 4.47. *Let H be a Hilbert space. If σ is continuous at $T \in B(H)$ and K is a compact operator commuting with T such that*

$$(i) \quad \partial\sigma(T + K) \cap (\pi_0(T) \setminus \pi_0(T)) = \emptyset, \text{ or}$$

$$(ii) \quad \text{for each } \lambda \in \partial\sigma(T + K) \cap (\overline{\pi_0(T)} \setminus \pi_0(T)), \lambda I - T \text{ is semi-Fredholm,}$$

then σ is continuous at $T + K$.

Proof. We first show that $T + K$ satisfies Browder's theorem. By Theorem 4.32, the continuity of σ at T implies that T satisfies Browder's theorem. Let $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K) \setminus \sigma_w(T + K)$.

If $\lambda \in \sigma(T)$, then $\lambda \in \sigma(T) \setminus \sigma_w(T)$ and hence $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$. Thus $\lambda I - T$ is a Weyl operator with finite ascent and descent. When $\lambda \notin \sigma(T)$, this statement is also true. Therefore, since T commutes with K , it follows that $\lambda I - (T + K)$ is a Weyl operator with finite ascent and descent, and consequently $\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K)$. Now, by reviewing the proof of Theorem 4.46, we see that in order to complete the proof of this corollary it suffices to verify that

$$\sigma(T + K) \cap \overline{\pi_0(T)} \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

whenever $T_n \rightarrow T + K$. Let $\lambda \in \sigma(T + K) \cap \overline{\pi_0(T)}$. If $\lambda \in \text{int } \sigma(T + K)$ or $\lambda \in \pi_0(T)$, then $\lambda \in \overline{\pi_0(T + K)}$ because $TK = KT$. By Lemma 4.25,

$$\overline{\pi_0(T + K)} \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

and hence $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$.

If $\lambda \notin \text{int } \sigma(T + K)$ and $\lambda \notin \pi_0(T)$, then $\lambda \in \partial\sigma(T + K) \cap (\overline{\pi_0(T)} \setminus \pi_0(T))$. This would be a contradiction if hypothesis (i) is assumed. On the other hand, if hypothesis (ii) is assumed, we obtain that $\lambda \in \pi_0(T + K)$ and therefore $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(T_n)$. □

Corollary 4.48. *Let H be a Hilbert space. If σ is continuous at $T \in B(H)$, then σ is continuous at $T + K$ for every $K \in K(H)$ such that*

$$\text{int } \sigma(T + K) \subset \sigma(T) \quad \text{and} \quad \text{iso } \sigma(T) \subset \text{iso } \sigma(T + K).$$

Proof. It is easy to see that

$$\text{int } (\sigma(T + K) \setminus \sigma_w(T + K)) = \emptyset.$$

As in the previous corollary, we have

$$\sigma(T + K) \cap \overline{\pi_0(T)} \subset \liminf \sigma(T_n),$$

where $T_n \rightarrow T + K$, since $\pi_0(T) \subset \pi_0(T + K)$, which follows from the fact that

$$\text{iso } \sigma(T) \subset \text{iso } \sigma(T + K).$$

□

Chapter 5

Spectral Properties of Matrix Operators

In this chapter we study some spectral properties of upper triangular matrix operators from the spectral properties of their diagonal.

5.1 Stability of the Spectrum and the Approximate Point Spectrum for the Operator M_C

For $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$, define the operator M_C on $X \oplus Y$ by

$$M_C = \begin{bmatrix} A & C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix}.$$

Many mathematicians have studied spectral properties of the operator M_C through the spectral properties of the operators A and B . In this section we are concerned with studying some inclusion relations for $\Sigma(M_C)$ with respect to $\Sigma(A)$ and $\Sigma(B)$, for $\Sigma \in \{\sigma, \sigma_{ap}, \sigma_{su}, \sigma_e, \sigma_w\}$.

Lemma 5.1 ([32, Lemma 1]). *If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$ are both invertible, then M_C is invertible for every $C \in B(Y, X)$.*

Proof. The inverse of M_C is

$$\begin{bmatrix} A^{-1} & -A^{-1}CB^{-1} \\ 0 & B^{-1} \end{bmatrix}.$$

□

As an immediate consequence of this lemma we obtain that for every $C \in B(Y, X)$,

$$\sigma(M_C) \subseteq \sigma(A) \cup \sigma(B). \tag{5.1}$$

This inclusion may be strict. Indeed, consider the unilateral shift $U \in B(\ell^2(\mathbb{N}))$ defined in Example 4.38, and let T be the operator defined on $\ell^2(\mathbb{N}) \oplus \ell^2(\mathbb{N})$ by

$$T = \begin{bmatrix} U & I - UU^* \\ 0 & U^* \end{bmatrix}.$$

This is a unitary operator, hence $\sigma(T) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : |\lambda| = 1\}$, however,

$$\sigma(U) \cup \sigma(U^*) = \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : |\lambda| \leq 1\}.$$

Thus,

$$\sigma(T) \subsetneq \sigma(U) \cup \sigma(U^*).$$

On the other hand, when X and Y are finite-dimensional Banach spaces, we have

$$\sigma(M_C) = \sigma(A) \cup \sigma(B),$$

for every $C \in B(Y, X)$. Indeed, if $\lambda - M_C$ is invertible, then from the following equality

$$\lambda - M_C = \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda - B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & C \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \lambda - A & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}, \quad (5.2)$$

we obtain that $\lambda - A$ is left invertible and $\lambda - B$ is right invertible. But since X and Y are finite-dimensional, it follows that $\lambda - A$ and $\lambda - B$ are invertible.

For other parts of the spectrum, inclusion (5.1) also holds, as shown below. See references [32], [46], [23], and [22] for a more complete study of this topic.

Proposition 5.2. *For $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$, the following inclusion holds:*

$$\sigma_e(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_e(A) \cup \sigma_e(B). \quad (5.3)$$

In particular, if $A \in \Phi(X)$ and $B \in \Phi(Y)$, then for every $C \in B(Y, X)$,

$$M_C \in \Phi(X \oplus Y) \quad \text{and} \quad i(M_C) = i(A) + i(B).$$

Proof. Let $M = \begin{bmatrix} A & 0 \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix}$. Since

$$N(\lambda - M) = N(\lambda - A) \oplus N(\lambda - B)$$

and

$$R(\lambda - M) = R(\lambda - A) \oplus R(\lambda - B),$$

it follows that

$$\sigma_e(M) \subseteq \sigma_e(A) \cup \sigma_e(B).$$

Now observe that

$$\begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & nI \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A & C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} I & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{n}I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A & \frac{1}{n}C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \rightarrow M \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Therefore, since σ_e is upper semicontinuous (see Theorem 4.15), it follows that for every

$\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a natural number N_ε such that

$$\sigma_\varepsilon \left(\begin{bmatrix} A & \frac{1}{n}C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \right) \subseteq (\sigma_\varepsilon(M))_\varepsilon,$$

for every $n \geq N_\varepsilon$. It is known that similar operators have the same essential spectrum. Thus, for every $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$\sigma_\varepsilon(M_C) = \sigma_\varepsilon \left(\begin{bmatrix} A & \frac{1}{N_\varepsilon}C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \right) \subseteq (\sigma_\varepsilon(M))_\varepsilon.$$

Hence,

$$\sigma_\varepsilon(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_\varepsilon(M).$$

Now suppose that $A \in \Phi(X)$ and $B \in \Phi(Y)$. By inclusion (5.3), $M_C \in \Phi(X \oplus Y)$. This implies that

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & \frac{1}{n}C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \in \Phi(X \oplus Y) \quad \text{and} \quad i \left(\begin{bmatrix} A & \frac{1}{n}C \\ 0 & B \end{bmatrix} \right) = i(M_C).$$

Clearly, M also belongs to $\Phi(X \oplus Y)$, and thus by continuity of the index we obtain

$$i(M_C) = i(M) = i(A) + i(B).$$

□

As an immediate consequence of this proposition we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 5.3. *For $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$, we have*

$$\sigma_w(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_w(A) \cup \sigma_w(B).$$

The previous inclusion also holds for the Browder spectrum:

Corollary 5.4. *Let $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$. Then*

$$\sigma_b(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_b(A) \cup \sigma_b(B).$$

Proof. Suppose that $\lambda \in \sigma_b(M_C)$ and $\lambda \notin \sigma_b(A) \cup \sigma_b(B)$. Then $\lambda - A$ and $\lambda - B$ are Browder operators. Now, since $\sigma(M_C) \subseteq \sigma(A) \cup \sigma(B)$, it follows that $\lambda \in \text{iso } \sigma(M_C)$. Moreover, because $\sigma_w(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_w(A) \cup \sigma_w(B)$, we have $\lambda - M_C \in \Phi(X)$ and $i(\lambda - M_C) = 0$. Thus, by Remark 1.24 (c), M_C has SVEP at λ , and by Theorem 1.30, $p(\lambda - M_C) < \infty$. Now, by Theorem 1.20 (d), $q(\lambda - M_C) < \infty$. This implies that $\lambda - M_C$ is a Browder operator, which is a contradiction. □

Theorem 5.5. *The operator M_C is invertible for some $C \in B(Y, X)$ if and only if $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$ satisfy the following conditions:*

- (i) $A \in G_l(B(X))$;
- (ii) $B \in G_r(B(Y))$;

(iii) $X/R(A) \cong N(B)$.

Proof. See [32, Theorem 2]. □

Corollary 5.6. *If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$, then*

$$\bigcap_{C \in B(Y, X)} \sigma(M_C) = \sigma_l(A) \cup \sigma_r(B) \cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : N(\lambda - B) \not\cong X/R(\lambda - A)\}.$$

Corollary 5.7. *If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$, then*

$$(\sigma(A) \cup \sigma(B)) \setminus \sigma(M_C) \subseteq \sigma(A) \cap \sigma(B), \quad (5.4)$$

for every $C \in B(Y, X)$.

Using equality (5.2) and the fact that

$$\alpha(\lambda - B) \neq \beta(\lambda - A) \quad \text{implies} \quad \lambda \in \sigma_e(M_C),$$

we can prove that, similarly to (5.4), the following also holds:

$$(\sigma_e(A) \cup \sigma_e(B)) \setminus \sigma_e(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_e(A) \cap \sigma_e(B). \quad (5.5)$$

Theorem 5.8. *$M_C \in W(X \oplus Y)$ for some $C \in B(Y, X)$ if and only if $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$ satisfy the following conditions:*

- (i) $A \in \Phi_+(X)$ and $R(A)$ is complemented in X ;
- (ii) $B \in \Phi_-(Y)$ and $N(B)$ is complemented in Y ;
- (iii) $N(A) \oplus N(B) \cong X/R(A) \oplus Y/R(B)$.

Proof. See [23, Theorem 3.6]. □

Corollary 5.9. *If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$, then*

$$\bigcap_{C \in B(Y, X)} \sigma_w(M_C) = \sigma_{le}(A) \cup \sigma_{re}(B) \cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : N(\lambda - A) \oplus N(\lambda - B) \not\cong X/R(\lambda - A) \oplus Y/R(\lambda - B)\}.$$

Corollary 5.10. *For $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$, the following holds:*

$$(\sigma_w(A) \cup \sigma_w(B)) \setminus \sigma_w(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_w(A) \cap \sigma_w(B). \quad (5.6)$$

Proposition 5.11. *Let $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$ be arbitrary operators. If $p(A) = \infty$, then $p(M_C) = \infty$, and if $q(B) = \infty$, then $q(M_C) = \infty$.*

Proof. If $p(A) = \infty$, then for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, there exists $x_n \in X$ such that

$$x_n \in N(A^{n+1}) \setminus N(A^n).$$

Hence, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$x_n \oplus 0 \in N(M_C^{n+1}) \setminus N(M_C^n),$$

and therefore $p(M_C) = \infty$.

Now suppose that $q(B) = \infty$ and let

$$d := q(M_C) < \infty.$$

Since $q(B) = \infty$, there exists

$$z \in R(B^d) \setminus R(B^{d+1}),$$

that is, there exists $y \in Y$ such that

$$z = B^d y$$

and

$$z \neq B^{d+1} t \quad \text{for every } t \in Y.$$

Let $v = 0 \oplus y$. Observe that

$$M_C^d v = \tilde{x} \oplus B^d y$$

for some $\tilde{x} \in X$. Then

$$\tilde{x} \oplus B^d y \in R(M_C^d) = R(M_C^{d+1}),$$

so there exist $x_1 \in X$ and $y_1 \in Y$ such that

$$\tilde{x} \oplus B^d y = M_C^{d+1}(x_1 \oplus y_1).$$

But

$$M_C^{d+1}(x_1 \oplus y_1) = [A^{d+1}x_1 + \tilde{x}_1] \oplus B^{d+1}y_1$$

for some $\tilde{x}_1 \in X$. This implies that

$$z = B^d y = B^{d+1}y_1,$$

which is a contradiction. □

Corollary 5.12. *If $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$, then*

$$(\sigma_b(A) \cup \sigma_b(B)) \setminus \sigma_b(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_b(A) \cap \sigma_b(B). \quad (5.7)$$

Subsequently, we present a theorem as an immediate consequence of the previous results obtained in this section.

Theorem 5.13. *If $\Sigma \in \{\sigma, \sigma_e, \sigma_w, \sigma_b\}$, then*

$$\Sigma(M_C) \subseteq \Sigma(A) \cup \Gamma(B),$$

and if

$$\Sigma(A) \cap \Sigma(B) = \emptyset,$$

then

$$\Sigma(M_C) = \Sigma(A) \cup \Sigma(B).$$

For the approximate point spectrum and the surjective spectrum, there are no inclusions analogous to (5.4), (5.5), (5.6), and (5.7), as shown by the following proposition.

Proposition 5.14. *If $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $C \in B(Y, X)$, then*

$$(a) \quad \sigma_{ap}(A) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(A) \cup \sigma_{ap}(B),$$

$$(b) \quad \sigma_{su}(B) \subseteq \sigma_{su}(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_{su}(A) \cup \sigma_{su}(B).$$

Proof. (a) Let $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(A)$. Then there exists $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in X with $\|x_n\| = 1$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $(\lambda - A)x_n \rightarrow 0$. Observe that

$$(\lambda - M_C)(x_n \oplus 0) = (\lambda - A)x_n \oplus 0 \rightarrow 0 \oplus 0,$$

and $\|x_n \oplus 0\| = 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Thus, $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(M_C)$. The proof that

$$\sigma_{ap}(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(A) \cup \sigma_{ap}(B)$$

is exactly the same as the proof given in Proposition 5.2. □

We have already presented some results from [32] and [23] concerning the set

$$\bigcap_{C \in B(Y, X)} \tau(M_C), \quad \tau \in \{\sigma, \sigma_w\}.$$

Dragan S. Djordjević in [23] obtained similar results for other parts of the spectrum. In the following theorem, we present a variation of one of his results (the second part of Corollary 5.3) for the Banach space setting.

Theorem 5.15. *Let X and Y be Banach spaces. If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$, then*

$$\bigcap_{C \in B(Y, X)} \sigma_{ap}(M_C) \supseteq \sigma_{ap}(A) \cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : R(\lambda - A) = X \text{ and } R(\lambda - B) \text{ is not closed}\}$$

$$\cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : \beta(\lambda - A) = 0 \text{ and } \alpha(\lambda - B) > 0\}.$$

Proof. By Proposition 5.14 (a), $\sigma_{ap}(A) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(M_C)$.

If $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ is such that $R(\lambda - A) = X$ and $R(\lambda - B)$ is not closed, then since $R(\lambda - M_C) = X \oplus R(\lambda - B)$, it follows that $R(\lambda - M_C)$ is not closed; therefore, $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(M_C)$.

Now let $\lambda \in \mathbb{C}$ be such that $\beta(\lambda - A) = 0$ and $\alpha(\lambda - B) > 0$.

Case I: $N(C) \cap N(\lambda - B) \neq \{0\}$.

Take $y \in N(C) \cap N(\lambda - B)$ with $y \neq 0$. The vector $0 \oplus y$ is nonzero and

$$(\lambda - M_C)(0 \oplus y) = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda - A & C \\ 0 & \lambda - B \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ y \end{pmatrix} = Cy \oplus (\lambda - B)y = 0.$$

Hence, $\lambda \in \sigma_p(M_C) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(M_C)$.

Case II: $N(C) \cap N(\lambda - B) = \{0\}$.

Since $\alpha(\lambda - B) > 0$, the subspace $N(\lambda - B)$ is nontrivial, and this implies that

$$\overline{C(N(\lambda - B))} \neq \{0\},$$

because $N(C) \cap N(\lambda - B) = \{0\}$. Consider $w \in \overline{C(N(\lambda - B))}$ with $w \neq 0$. Clearly, $\lambda - A$ is surjective, since $\beta(\lambda - A) = 0$. Thus, there exists $x \in X$ such that $(\lambda - A)x = w$. On the other hand, there exists a sequence $\{z_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in $N(\lambda - B)$ such that $Cz_n \rightarrow w$. Observe that if $\|z_n\| \rightarrow 0$, then $Cz_n \rightarrow 0$, and consequently $w = 0$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, $\|z_n\| \not\rightarrow 0$. Hence, we may assume that there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\|z_n\| \geq \varepsilon$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

$$\|x \oplus (-z_n)\| \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sqrt{\|x\|^2 + \varepsilon^2},$$

for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Now, since

$$\begin{aligned} \left\| (\lambda - M_C) \frac{x \oplus (-z_n)}{\|x \oplus (-z_n)\|} \right\| &= \frac{1}{\|x \oplus (-z_n)\|} \left\| \begin{pmatrix} \lambda - A & C \\ 0 & \lambda - B \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ -z_n \end{pmatrix} \right\| \\ &= \frac{1}{\|x \oplus (-z_n)\|} \|(\lambda - A)x - Cz_n \oplus 0\| \\ &\leq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{\|x\|^2 + \varepsilon^2}} \|(\lambda - A)x - Cz_n\|, \end{aligned}$$

and since $Cz_n \rightarrow (\lambda - A)x$, it follows that

$$\left\| (\lambda - M_C) \frac{x \oplus (-z_n)}{\|x \oplus (-z_n)\|} \right\| \rightarrow 0.$$

Therefore, $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(M_C)$. □

By duality, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 5.16. *Let X and Y be Banach spaces. If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcap_{C \in B(Y, X)} \sigma_{su}(M_C) &\supseteq \sigma_{su}(B) \cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : R(\lambda - B) = X \text{ and } R(\lambda - A) \text{ is not closed}\} \\ &\cup \{\lambda \in \mathbb{C} : \alpha(\lambda - B) = 0 \text{ and } \beta(\lambda - A) > 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

5.2 Spectral Continuity on Upper Triangular Matrix Operators

S. V. Djordjević and Y. M. Han in [20] studied the continuity of the spectrum of M_C through the continuity of the spectrum of A and B . Following this idea, in this section we provide conditions for the continuity of the spectrum and the approximate point spectrum on the space of upper triangular matrix operators.

We begin this section with the following theorem, which generalizes [20, Theorem 2.1].

Theorem 5.17. *Let $A \in B(X)$, $B \in B(Y)$ and $\Sigma \in \{\sigma, \sigma_e, \sigma_w, \sigma_b\}$ be such that $\Sigma(A) \cap \Sigma(B) = \emptyset$. Then Σ is continuous at A and B if and only if Σ is continuous at M_C for every $C \in B(Y, X)$.*

Proof. Let $T_n = \begin{pmatrix} A_n & C_n \\ 0 & B_n \end{pmatrix}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, be such that $T_n \rightarrow M_C$.

\Rightarrow] Since $\Sigma(A) \cap \Sigma(B) = \emptyset$, there exists $\delta > 0$ such that $(\Sigma(A))_\delta \cap (\Sigma(B))_\delta = \emptyset$. Now, by Theorem 4.15, Σ is upper semicontinuous at A and B . Hence, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, $\Sigma(A_n) \subseteq (\Sigma(A))_\delta$ and $\Sigma(B_n) \subseteq (\Sigma(B))_\delta$. This implies that for every $n \geq n_0$, $\Sigma(A_n) \cap \Sigma(B_n) = \emptyset$, and therefore, $\Sigma(T_n) = \Sigma(A_n) \cup \Sigma(B_n)$, see Theorem 5.13. Thus,

$$\Sigma(M_C) = \Sigma(A) \cup \Sigma(B) \subseteq \liminf(\Sigma(A_n) \cup \Sigma(B_n)) = \liminf \Sigma(T_n).$$

[\Leftarrow] Suppose that Σ is continuous at M_C for every $C \in B(Y, X)$. We prove that Σ is continuous at A . Let $\lambda \in \Sigma(A)$. Since $\Sigma(A) \cap \Sigma(B) = \emptyset$, we have $\lambda \notin \Sigma(B)$, and $\lambda \in \Sigma(M_C)$. Since $\Sigma(M_C) \subseteq \liminf \Sigma(M_n)$, there exists a sequence $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $\lambda_n \rightarrow \lambda$ and $\lambda_n \in \Sigma(M_n) \subseteq \Sigma(A_n) \cup \Sigma(B_n)$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If there exists a strictly increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < \dots$ such that $\lambda_{n_k} \in \Sigma(B_{n_k})$, for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\lambda \in \limsup \Sigma(B_n) \subseteq \Sigma(B)$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, there exists $n_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lambda_n \in \Sigma(A_n)$, for every $n \geq n_1$. Hence, $\lambda \in \liminf \Sigma(A_n)$. Similarly, one proves that Σ is continuous at B . \square

In the previous theorem, M_C satisfies

$$\sigma(M_C) = \sigma(A) \cup \sigma(B).$$

This condition together with the continuity of σ at A and B is not sufficient to guarantee that σ is continuous at M_C . Indeed, let $U \in B(\ell^2(\mathbb{N}))$ be the operator defined in Example 4.38, and consider the operator M defined on $\ell^2(\mathbb{N}) \oplus \ell^2(\mathbb{N})$ by

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} U & 0 \\ 0 & U^* \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.8)$$

This operator satisfies $\sigma(M) = \sigma(U) \cup \sigma(U^*)$, and by Proposition 4.22, both U and U^* are points of continuity of σ . However, in Example 4.38 we already proved that M is not a point of continuity of σ .

Observe that if $T_n = \begin{pmatrix} A_n & C_n \\ 0 & B_n \end{pmatrix}$ is a sequence of upper triangular matrix operators such that $T_n \rightarrow M_C$, and for some $N \in \mathbb{N}$, $\sigma(T_n) = \sigma(A_n) \cup \sigma(B_n)$, for every $n \geq N$, then $\sigma(A_n) \rightarrow \sigma(A)$ and $\sigma(B_n) \rightarrow \sigma(B)$ imply that $\sigma(T_n) \rightarrow \sigma(M_C)$.

S. V. Djordjević and Y. M. Han proved in [20, Theorem 2.4] that, on Hilbert spaces, σ is continuous at M_C whenever M_C satisfies Browder's theorem and σ_{ap} and σ_{su} are continuous at A and B , respectively. A more general result is the following.

Theorem 5.18. *If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$ satisfy:*

- (i) $\sigma(A) = \sigma_{ap}(A)$;
- (ii) σ_{ap} is continuous at A ;
- (iii) σ is continuous at B .

Then σ is continuous at M_C for every $C \in B(Y, X)$.

Proof. Recall that the spectrum function is upper semicontinuous at every operator. Thus, it is enough to show that σ is lower semicontinuous at M_C . Let $\{M_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of upper triangular matrix operators, $M_n = \begin{pmatrix} A_n & C_n \\ 0 & B_n \end{pmatrix}$, such that $M_n \rightarrow M_C$. Take an arbitrary $\lambda \in \sigma(M_C)$. Since $\sigma(M_C) \subseteq \sigma(A) \cup \sigma(B)$, it follows that $\lambda \in \sigma(A)$ or $\lambda \in \sigma(B)$.

Case I: $\lambda \in \sigma(A)$.

By hypothesis (i), $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(A)$, and by the continuity of σ_{ap} at A , $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{ap}(A_n)$. According to Proposition 5.14 (a), $\sigma_{ap}(A_n) \subseteq \sigma_{ap}(M_n) \subseteq \sigma(M_n)$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Consequently, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(M_n)$.

Case II: $\lambda \in \sigma(B) \setminus \sigma(A)$.

Since σ is continuous at B , for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we may choose $\lambda_n \in \sigma(B_n)$ such that $\lambda_n \rightarrow \lambda$. Suppose that there exists a strictly increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \dots$ such that for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lambda_{n_k} \notin \sigma(M_{n_k})$. Observe that $\lambda_{n_k} \in (\sigma(A_{n_k}) \cup \sigma(B_{n_k})) \setminus \sigma(M_{n_k})$, thus, by Corollary 5.7, $\lambda_{n_k} \in \sigma(A_{n_k}) \cap \sigma(B_{n_k})$. Therefore, for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lambda_{n_k} \in \sigma(A_{n_k})$. This implies that $\lambda \in \limsup \sigma(A_n)$. Then, by the upper semicontinuity of σ , it follows that $\lambda \in \sigma(A)$, which is a contradiction. Consequently, there exists $n_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for every $n \geq n_0$, $\lambda_n \in \sigma(M_n)$. Therefore, $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma(M_n)$. \square

Let M be the operator defined in (5.8). Observe that

$$M^* = \begin{pmatrix} U^* & 0 \\ 0 & U \end{pmatrix}.$$

From Proposition 4.22, we see that σ_{su} is continuous at U and σ_{ap} is continuous at U^* . Thus, since $\sigma(U^*) = \sigma_{ap}(U^*)$, it follows from Theorem 5.18 that σ is continuous at M^* . Note that $\Xi(M^*) = \Xi(U^*)$. Now, the operator U^* does not have the SVEP at 0 (see the proof of [43, Theorem 7(c)]), and therefore $0 \in \Xi(M^*)$. Moreover, since $i(M^*) = i(U^*) + i(U) = 0$, it follows that $0 \in \Xi(M^*) \setminus \sigma_w(M^*)$. Therefore, M^* does not satisfy Browder's theorem. This example shows that Theorem 5.18 is a generalization of [20, Theorem 2.4].

Remark 5.19. In Theorem 5.18, hypothesis (i) may be replaced by the condition that A^* has the SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{sF}(T)$.

Let H be a Hilbert space. Recall that if $A \in B(H)$ is a point of continuity of the spectrum, then for every $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(A) \setminus \overline{\rho_{sF}^\pm(A) \cup \pi_0(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(A)$. Thus, by Corollary 4.30 and Theorem 5.18 together with Remark 5.19, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 5.20. *Let H and K be Hilbert spaces. If $A \in B(H)$ and $B \in B(K)$ satisfy:*

- (i) A^* has the SVEP at every $\lambda \notin \sigma_{lre}(A)$;
- (ii) σ is continuous at both A and B .

Then σ is continuous at M_C for every $C \in B(K, H)$.

We conclude this section by establishing a theorem similar to Theorem 5.18, but now in terms of the approximate point spectrum.

Theorem 5.21. *Let X and Y be Banach spaces. If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$ satisfy:*

- (i) $\sigma(A) = \sigma_{ap}(A)$;
- (ii) σ_{ap} is continuous at both A and B .

Then σ_{ap} is continuous at M_C for every $C \in B(Y, X)$.

Proof. Let $\{M_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of upper triangular matrix operators, $M_n = \begin{pmatrix} A_n & C_n \\ 0 & B_n \end{pmatrix}$, converging to M_C .

Let $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(M_C)$. By Proposition 5.14 (a), $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(A)$ or $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(B)$.

Case I: $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(A)$.

As in the proof of Theorem 5.18, by the continuity of σ_{ap} at A , we have

$$\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(A) \subseteq \liminf \sigma_{ap}(A_n) \subseteq \liminf \sigma_{ap}(M_n).$$

Case II: $\lambda \in \sigma_{ap}(B) \setminus \sigma_{ap}(A)$.

The point λ does not belong to $\sigma(A)$, since $\sigma(A) = \sigma_{ap}(A)$. Now, by the continuity of σ_{ap} at B , there exists a sequence $\{\lambda_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $\lambda_n \rightarrow \lambda$ and $\lambda_n \in \sigma_{ap}(B_n)$, for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If there exists a strictly increasing sequence of natural numbers $n_1 < n_2 < n_3 < \dots$ such that $\lambda_{n_k} \in \sigma(A_{n_k})$, for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\lambda \in \limsup \sigma(A_n)$. Thus, by the upper semicontinuity of σ , $\lambda \in \sigma(A)$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, there exists a natural number n_0 such that for every $n \geq n_0$, $\lambda_n - A_n$ is invertible. Let $n \geq n_0$. Since $\lambda_n \in \sigma_{ap}(B_n)$, it follows that $R(\lambda_n - B_n)$ is not closed or $\lambda_n - B_n$ is not injective. If $R(\lambda_n - B_n)$ is not closed, then Theorem 5.15, together with the fact that $R(\lambda_n - A_n) = X$, implies that $\lambda_n \in \sigma_{ap}(M_n)$. Now, if $\lambda_n - B_n$ is not injective, then $\alpha(\lambda_n - B_n) > 0$, while $\beta(\lambda_n - A_n) = 0$, since $\lambda_n - A_n$ is invertible. Thus, by Theorem 5.15, we again obtain $\lambda_n \in \sigma_{ap}(M_n)$. Consequently, for every $n \geq n_0$, $\lambda_n \in \sigma_{ap}(M_n)$, which implies that $\lambda \in \liminf \sigma_{ap}(M_n)$. \square

By duality we obtain the following theorem.

Theorem 5.22. *Let X and Y be Banach spaces. If $A \in B(X)$ and $B \in B(Y)$ satisfy:*

(i) $\sigma(B) = \sigma_{su}(B)$;

(ii) σ_{su} is continuous at both A and B .

Then σ_{su} is continuous at M_C for every $C \in B(Y, X)$.

Conclusions

Since the spectrum of an operator is a fundamental set for its analysis, and given the difficulty involved in determining it, spectral continuity becomes an essential tool for studying it in an approximate manner.

This thesis gathers a series of both known and new results concerning continuity, especially of the spectrum and the approximate point spectrum, which are presented in detail. In particular:

1. It is proved that the approximate point spectrum function σ_{ap} is continuous at an operator $T \in B(X)$ whenever T^* has the SVEP at every point outside $\sigma_{lre}(T)$ and, for each $\lambda \in \sigma_{lre}(T) \setminus \overline{\phi_+(T)}$ and every $\varepsilon > 0$, the disk $B(\lambda, \varepsilon)$ contains a connected component of $\sigma_{lre}(T)$. This result is included in [40].
2. A relationship between spectral continuity and Browder's theorem is established. More specifically, it is shown that if T is an operator defined on a Hilbert space and T is a point of continuity of the spectrum, then T satisfies Browder's theorem.
3. Conditions are determined for the continuity of the spectrum under the perturbation $T + K$ of the operator T by a compact operator K . The results concerning item 2 and this item led to the article [41].
4. We have also devoted attention to the study of the continuity of the spectrum and the approximate point spectrum on the class of upper triangular matrix operators. It is proved that if M_C is defined by

$$M_C := \begin{pmatrix} A & C \\ 0 & B \end{pmatrix},$$

and A, B are points of continuity of σ_{ap} , then σ_{ap} , viewed as a function restricted to the class of upper triangular matrix operators, is continuous at M_C whenever $\sigma(A) = \sigma_{ap}(A)$, or A^* has the SVEP at every point outside $\sigma_{sF}(A)$.

Now, if the operators A, B , and C are defined on Hilbert spaces, then we also have that σ is continuous at M_C whenever σ is continuous at both A and B , and A^* has the SVEP at every point outside $\sigma_{sF}(A)$. These results can be found in [40].

We now comment on some open problems that naturally arise from the results obtained in this thesis.

- Let $S^*(X) = \{T \in B(X) : T^* \text{ has the SVEP}\}$. It is worth mentioning that many classes of operators are contained in $S^*(X)$. In this work, we established several sufficient conditions for the continuity of σ_{ap} at operators $T \in S^*(X)$. A natural question that arises is whether some of these assumptions, or perhaps other conditions, are also necessary for the continuity of σ_{ap} at $T \in S^*(X)$.
- Can the continuity results obtained for σ and σ_{ap} be extended to other types of spectra, such as the essential spectrum, the Weyl spectrum, or the Browder spectrum, in the setting of upper triangular operator matrices?
- Can the results obtained in this work be applied to the study of spectral continuity for operators $T \in B(Z)$, when the Banach space Z admits a decomposition $Z = X \oplus Y$, where X and Y are closed subspaces of Z and X is invariant under T ?

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